

Atlantic Ecosystems Assessment, Forecasting & Sustainability

Deliverable number 3.2 - Pluralistic valuation of ecosystem services

Dissemination level: Public

Related Work Package	WP3 - Marine ecosystem health and services
Related task(s)	T3.2 Socio-cultural and economic valuation of ecosystem services
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Due date	31.08.2024
Submission date	20.12.2024
Type	Report
Status and version	Final v1.0

Declaration: Any work or result described therein is a genuine output of the AtlantECO project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant.

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1 Version History

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
0.1	F. Bosello (CMCC)	Section 4	23/07/2024
0.2	S. Libralato, S. Zunino, D. L. Rico-Velez D. Canu (OGS) J. Wilson (Uni. Liverpool) A. Katavouta (NOC)	Section 6 & 7	18/10/2024
0.3	G.B. Ainsworth, P. Pita, A. Campos, S. Villasante (USC) A. Ospina-Alvarez (UIB-CSIC)	Section 5	29/10/2024
0.4	S. Libralato, S. Zunino (OGS) G.B. Ainsworth, S. Villasante, (USC) F. Bosello (CMCC)	Section 8	20/12/2024
0.5	G.B. Ainsworth, S. Villasante, (USC) S. Libralato, S. Zunino (OGS) F. Bosello (CMCC)	Section 2, 3	19/12/2024
0.6	S. Villasante, G.B. Ainsworth (USC)	Final formatting and review	20/12/2024
0.7	C. de Majo, S. Peasant, D. Iudicone	First interim review	26/11/2024
0.8	S. Libralato, S. Zunino, D. L. Rico-Velez D. Canu (OGS) J. Wilson (Uni. Liverpool) A. Katavouta (NOC) G.B. Ainsworth, P. Pita, A. Campos, S. Villasante (USC) A. Ospina-Alvarez (UIB-CSIC) F. Bosello (CMCC)	Review addressing comments received	20/12/2024
1.0	C. de Majo, S. Peasant, D. Iudicone	Quality check and submission	20/12/2024

2 Executive summary

This deliverable contains a comprehensive evaluation of selected ecosystem services provided by ocean ecosystems under critical pressures based on research conducted in Task 3.2 Socio-cultural and economic valuation of ecosystem services. CMCC conducted an economic evaluation of provisioning and other services linked to fishery, aquaculture, bio-prospecting, renewable energy and tourism activity by inspecting national statistics to highlight their contribution to the production of national GDP (Section 4). USC (leading) coordinated the task and conducted a socio-cultural evaluation of cultural services with UIB-CSIC (Section 5). OGS conducted a quantification of regulating services to support these economic and socio-cultural evaluations including an assessment of carbon sequestration services of the Atlantic Ocean (Section 6) and an assessment of sequestration services from accumulation rates and stocks regarding coastal Atlantic blue carbon ecosystems (Section 7). Overall, the deliverable addresses the lack of scientific knowledge in analytical frameworks for effective policy-making to achieve sustainable environmental management.

In Section 4, CMCC collated the available data on the economic values of provisioning services from capture fisheries, aquaculture, minerals, non-renewable/renewable energy, and coastal tourism, focusing on the material goods traded in markets that originated from marine ecosystems for which market prices exist and that can be used as an indicator for the estimate of the value of the ecosystem service. We calculated the monetary value of marine provisioning services provided by capture fisheries, aquaculture, minerals, non-renewable/renewable energy and coastal tourism attributable to the Atlantic sea basin.

Our results demonstrate that coastal tourism provides the highest Gross Value Added (GVA) (US\$) for most countries among the sectors analysed, while fisheries and aquaculture generally provide the lowest, although the contributions vary enormously across countries. Low-income Atlantic African countries tend to receive GVA benefits from fisheries and sometimes from minerals and non-renewables. Conversely, the wealthiest countries in temperate areas receive GVA benefits from tourism.

In Section 5, USC and UIB-CSIC evaluated cultural ecosystem services, focusing on the conservation, and tourism and recreation sectors to understand the (dis)benefits provided by marine protected areas and marine tourism sites to visitors through practices associated with cultural, spiritual and historical heritage, provision of nature-based recreation, and creation of opportunities for science and education. We selected 23 iconic marine sites that are geographically distributed around the coastlines, islands and high seas and that represent various biogeographic provinces and ecoregions throughout the Atlantic Ocean. We collected and analysed data derived from 6,319 Google Maps reviews pertaining to these sites to identify the socio-cultural values held for each site individually and collectively. We also analysed visitor data and entrance fees to calculate tourism revenue raised by each site.

Reviewers reported almost 80 different kinds of pursuits, mostly relating to recreational activities underlining the importance of marine areas for providing opportunities for people to play and exercise. Reviewers were mostly satisfied with their visits, with 90% of remarks being positive and sites receiving an average rating score of 4.7 out of a possible 5. Reviewers mostly appreciated Sense of Place, Tourism & Recreation, Livelihoods & Economies, Biodiversity and Clean Waters, as well as 'clean site'. However, 10% of reviews were composed of negative remarks and reviewers identified various disbenefits received from the sites including: experiencing overcrowding of tourists, presence of marine litter on land and in the ocean, unsatisfying wildlife interactions, degraded environments, poor infrastructure or services, and high entrance fees.

Our analysis also identified perceptions about the impacts of plastics on cultural services. These mainly related to the presence of plastics spoiling reviewers' recreational activities such as enjoying scenic beauty (aesthetic appreciation). These plastics were sometimes said to be found in the ocean (Clean Waters) but were mostly described as being on beaches or nearby areas (Sense of Place - Lasting Special Places: clean site). We uncovered that 18 of the 23 iconic sites distributed around the Atlantic Ocean were facing socio-environmental threats at the time of our analysis. These threats were caused by local human activities, anthropogenic impacts, or climate changes and over half of the sites were perceived as suffering from multiple kinds of threats.

The numerous and diverse wellbeing benefits received by site reviewers and our estimate of annual visitor revenue of nearly US\$207 million reveal the extent of public desire to visit iconic marine sites and a willingness to pay for cultural services provided by healthy sites. This also hints at the amount of public funds for site management, conservation and promotion that could be lost should all tourists avoid these sites due to the significant threats we identified.

In Section 6, OGS, Univ. Liverpool and NOC investigated the regulating services of the ocean's carbon sequestration process, focusing on the biological carbon pump (BCP), which accounts for about 70% of the ocean's carbon sequestration capacity. We estimated the carbon storage for the Atlantic Ocean by applying two methods. First, we applied a method based on model assessments of Particulate Organic Carbon (POC) fluxes and of mineralization of POC. We assessed the carbon flux of POC at 1000 m depth and the inventory of sequestered carbon using data from three Earth system models (ESM) at the present time. Second, we applied a method that integrates the contribution of gravitational, migrant and mixing pumps, using models and observations to quantify carbon export and sequestration through the ocean's BCP.

From the three different ESM models we estimated the total amount of POC that reaches 1000 m in the Atlantic Ocean varies between 0.47 PgCy⁻¹ and 0.18 PgCy⁻¹. We identified that the Atlantic Ocean exhibits different patterns of carbon flux into the deep sea that vary with the latitudinal gradient. Low carbon export is particularly evident in the subtropical gyres while the tropical and upwelling areas are characterized by higher productivity. The North Atlantic is another region with high carbon exports whereas the Southern Ocean is the zone where the models are more uncertain, however, high carbon export in the sub-Antarctic region is still evident due to the highly productive spring bloom. By shifting the focus from fluxes to inventory stock, this assessment provides a more comprehensive understanding of the processes themselves and their long-term contribution to ocean carbon sequestration. The C_{soft}, which represents the total carbon stored in the Atlantic as an average among the 3 ES Models is 310.72 PgC, which represents 17% of the global carbon sequestration.

We also conducted an economic valuation of the benefits of the Atlantic ecosystems in relation to their carbon storage services using the concept of Social Cost of Carbon (SCC) which measures the damage cost of emitting an additional unit of carbon dioxide or other equivalent greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. Three factors are particularly relevant in determining the social cost of carbon: how damages are aggregated intra-temporally across different individuals, groups or communities; when the unit emission occurs; and choice of discount rate. The total carbon stock of the Atlantic is in the order of 260-375 PgC (average 319.49 PgC; about 15-20% of the global ocean carbon stock), with the average value of this output estimated at between US\$46.6 trillion to US\$171 trillion.

In Section 7, OGS assessed regulating services based on an analysis of blue carbon sequestration from accumulation rates and stocks of 'blue carbon ecosystems' (BCE) in the Atlantic Ocean. These include habitats such as salt marshes, tidal flats, seagrass meadows and mangroves which can provide important climate regulating services as nature-based solutions to mitigate climate change by achieving carbon removal from the atmosphere. We calculated carbon storage at the Atlantic scale by analysing the global databases of BCE habitats to determine their spatial extent then converting their extension to carbon accumulation rates and carbon storage for each ecosystem through coefficients extracted from literature.

We identified that the total area of BCEs in the Atlantic is 273,600 km². Seagrass has the largest extent, covering 54% of this area, with a total of 145,814.92 km². Tidal flats have an extension of 42,719.5 km² representing 15% of the BCE area in the Atlantic, and 19.52% of the global extent. Mangroves cover 57,420.60 km² in the Atlantic Ocean, representing 21.95% of the area and 41.73% of the global extent, while salt marshes are the least extended BCE in the Atlantic Ocean, covering 28,399.54 km², representing 10.57% of the Atlantic basin and 68.18% of the global extent. The total carbon accumulation rate in the Atlantic is estimated to be 46.81 TgC^y⁻¹, while the total carbon stock, which represents the total carbon sequestered below-ground in Atlantic coastal ecosystems, is estimated to be 4.5 PgC, which represents 44 % of the global Cstock estimates (7.6 PgC).

However, these ecosystems are heavily impacted by human activities. All BCE have declined over the last century, mainly due to aquaculture, land-use change and land reclamation. Given increasing attention to this topic, many efforts have been made to produce accurate estimates of global BCE. Significant uncertainty persists since the available distributional data is highly skewed geographically (and historically) and many components required to conduct complete assessments are lacking.

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction

This report offers an assessment of provisioning, cultural and regulating services provided by marine ecosystems in the Atlantic Ocean.

Ecosystem services are defined as the benefits that humans obtain from natural systems (MEA, 2005). More specifically, this refers to the flow of services, goods and “other benefits” that humans receive from nature, that have an impact on welfare and wellbeing, and thus from which a value can be derived. In other words, the components of the natural environment considered “useful” to humans (Villasante et al. 2023).

The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA 2005) has classified ecosystem services into four broad categories:

Provisioning Ecosystem Services	The physical products that can be obtained from ecosystems, e.g., food and raw materials.
Regulating Ecosystem Services	The benefits obtained from the regulation of ecosystem processes, e.g., climate regulation from carbon sequestration.
Supporting Ecosystem Services	The supporting services that are necessary for the provision of all the other ecosystem services, e.g. nutrient cycling
Cultural Ecosystem Services	The non-material benefits that can be obtained from ecosystems, e.g., sense of inspiration.

The economic evaluation of provisioning services (Section 4) collates the available data on the values of capture fisheries, aquaculture, minerals, non-renewable/renewable energy, and coastal tourism. It primarily focuses on the values of the material goods that are traded in markets originating from marine ecosystems for which market prices exist and can be used as an indicator for the estimated value of the services discussed.

The assessment of cultural services at the Atlantic level (Section 5) explores the ways that visitors to different types of marine protected areas (MPAs) and marine tourism sites distributed around Atlantic Ocean coastlines, islands and high seas culturally engage with the ocean. The approach collected a large amount of information at a relatively low cost. Analysis of Google Maps reviews for 23 iconic marine sites facilitates the identification of perceived (dis)benefits received by reviewers from these sites. The estimated revenue raised by case study sites based on most recent visitor numbers and entrance fees is also presented. To understand potential threats to iconic marine sites, perceptions about the impacts of plastics on the case study sites are examined and at risk and vulnerable hot spots due to climate, local human activity or anthropogenic impact are identified.

The quantification of regulating services to support the economic and socio-cultural evaluations includes an assessment of the carbon sequestration service of the Atlantic Ocean (Sections 6 and 7). We calculated the particulate organic carbon flux at 1000 metres and total carbon stored in the Atlantic Ocean (Section 6). Additionally, we investigate coastal Atlantic blue carbon ecosystems by assessing sequestration services from accumulation rates and stocks providing a detailed overview of the extent of area coverage and carbon storage in total and by country (Section 7).

4 Provisioning services provided by the Atlantic Ocean

4.1 Background

This section focuses on the economic value of provisioning services provided by the Atlantic Ocean. It collates the available data on the values of capture fisheries, aquaculture, minerals, non-renewable/renewable energy, and coastal tourism. It primarily focuses on the values of the material goods that are traded in markets that originated from marine ecosystems for which market prices exist and can be used as an indicator for the estimate of the value of the ecosystem service. For example, this is the justification behind selecting the value of marine fish landings as an indicator for the value of seafood as a provisioning ecosystem service.

4.2 Methods

Below we present a more detailed description of the specific provisioning services that are valued.

· **Seafood**

Practically all ecosystems provide the necessary conditions for growing and harvesting food. Marine ecosystems provide the habitat and conditions for the capture and cultivation of marine fish which is a key element of the human diet worldwide. Moreover, the sector also derives crucial cash earnings and employment from the food services (FAO 2022).

· **Minerals and non-living resources**

Marine ecosystems provide a wide range of raw materials, minerals, and resources that are useful and valuable to humans, for example, biofuels, oil and gas, medicinal resources.

· **Tourism**

Another ecosystem service with a direct use value that can be valued using observable market transactions is coastal tourism. Tourists are drawn to coastal destinations for many reasons, including marine activities, beaches, and biodiversity amenities. This type of tourism is thus strongly supported by the underlying marine ecosystems. Tourists reveal their appreciation and value for marine ecosystems by the time spent and expenditure sustained during trips to and stays at coastal areas. Theoretically, this is classified as a cultural service. Nonetheless, for the purposes of this report, and due to the potential high economic value that can be associated, it was also included in the present scrutiny.

The data

The data accompanying this document has been collected from a variety of different sources, and hence it should be noted that values and their respective indicators may not always be comparable across countries, while caution should be used in summing up individual indicators to estimate an aggregate value.

The value of the ecosystem services in some countries can be fully attributed to the Atlantic sea basin. However, there are some countries that have several “facades”, e.g., Spain has both an Atlantic facade and a Mediterranean facade. In the cases when only the aggregated country coastal value was available, the share

attributed to the Atlantic region was estimated by using an “Atlantic ratio”. This ratio was calculated using firstly, if available, the proportion of GDP produced, or employment in the Atlantic areas of the country (administrative units with Atlantic coasts) with respect to the total coastal regions. Where unavailable, the ratio was calculated using the relative size of land cover of the Atlantic coastal areas with respect to all coastal regions.

Main data sources

For the EU Atlantic countries (Ireland, France, Spain, and Portugal), the data has been extracted from the EU blue economy report Annex 1, 2020. (European Commission 2020). The indicators extracted and reported are the following:

Gross Value Added (GVA) of living resources, GVA of oil, gas and minerals, and GVA of coastal tourism.^[1] The marine living resources encompass the harvesting of primary resources (capture fisheries and aquaculture), processing of fish products, and their distribution along the supply chain.^[2] The oil, gas and other minerals indicator provides an estimate of the value of offshore oil and gas extraction, and the extraction of minerals such as sand or gravel from the ocean.^[3] Coastal tourism, referring also to maritime tourism, includes values from the following activities: accommodation, transport, and other expenditures.

Data for the UK (England, Scotland, Wales, Northern Ireland, Isle of Man, Guernsey) on the value of seafood is represented by the indicator of commercial sea fisheries landings collected from the UK Sea Fisheries Statistics 2019, (Marine Management Organisation 2019). Data on the value of coastal tourism for the whole of the UK is represented by the indicator of coastal tourism expenditure, sourced from the ONS: Tourism and outdoor leisure accounts, natural capital, UK (2021b). The value of offshore wind energy produced, and oil and gas extraction are both sourced from the ONS, Marine accounts, natural capital, UK (2021a).

The data for Canada on the value of seafood is represented by the indicator of marine landings and aquaculture. This data was sourced from the OECD. The values of oil and gas and coastal tourism both come from Government of Canada statistics: “Canada’s oceans and the economic contribution of marine sectors” and refer to the GDP by sector (Statistics Canada 2021).

The data for the value of the US Atlantic provisioning services was sourced from: Ocean Economy data, National Ocean Economics Program^[4] based on ENOW Ocean economy and was already specific to the Atlantic Sea basin (The Eastern Cape Oceans Economy Strategic Roadmap 2019). Living resources are represented by the value of seafood provision which is calculated from the contribution to GDP of the following activities/industries: fish hatcheries & aquaculture, fishing, seafood markets, seafood processing. The values for tourism represent the contribution to GDP of coastal tourism, composed of spending in amusement and recreation services, boat dealers, eating and drinking places, hotels and lodging places, marina, recreational vehicle parks and campsites, scenic water tours, sporting goods retailers, zoos and aquaria. The values associated with minerals are the contribution to GDP of limestone, sand and gravel extraction from the ocean, and oil and gas exploration and production.

For many of the remaining countries, data availability was scarce, the only indicator available on the value of provisioning services is the value added of the fishing and aquaculture sector. This figure is used to estimate the value of seafood provisioning services in the respective countries and was sourced from the United

Nations Statistics Division GVA Fisheries, which in turn is based on National Accounts Official Country Data. Where possible, countries with multiple ocean facade values were attributed using the estimated “Atlantic ratio”.

In some cases, data on the value of coastal tourism and/or minerals was available at a regional level however not at the country level. For the Caribbean, data on the value of offshore oil and gas was sourced from Patil et al. (2016). The revenues of coastal and marine tourism in the Caribbean region were also sourced from Patil et al. (2016). For the African Atlantic zone, the value added of the offshore oil and gas sector was sourced from Union Africaine, “Stratégie de l’économie bleue de l’Afrique” (Union Africaine 2019).^[5]

^[1] Value added at factor costs (GVA) of the sector consists of the gross income from operating activities after adjusting to operating subsidies and indirect taxes.

^[2] Marine living resources comprises three subsectors that are further broken-down into: • Primary sector: Capture fisheries (small-scale coastal, large scale and industrial fleets) and Aquaculture (marine, freshwater and shellfish); • Processing of fish products: Processing and preservation of fish, crustaceans and molluscs; Prepared meals and dishes, Manufacture of oils and fats and Other food products; and • Distribution of fish products: Retail sale of fish, crustaceans and molluscs in specialised stores and Wholesale of other food, including fish, crustaceans and molluscs.

^[3] The GVA of the oil, gas and minerals sector includes the value of extraction of crude petroleum, Extraction of natural gas and support activities for petroleum and natural gas extraction; Other minerals: Operation of gravel and sand pits; mining of clays and kaolin, Extraction of salt and Support activities for other mining and quarrying

^[4] NOEP data is based on Economics: National Ocean Watch (ENOW) ocean data.

^[5] This figure included some Atlantic countries and Mozambique, but due to data unavailability it was not possible to calculate the value excluding Mozambique.

4.3 Results

All the data are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Estimates of the value of Marine Provisioning Services in the Atlantic Ocean (p= provisional value).

Country/Region	Indicator	Year	USD value	USD million	Ref
Ireland	GVA of living resources	2018	720,471,000	720	4
Ireland	GVA, Oil, gas, minerals	2018	4,724,400	5	4
Ireland	GVA, Coastal Tourism	2018	2,201,570,400	2202	4
Spain	GVA of living resources	2017	1,263,394,228	1263	4
Spain	GVA, Oil, gas, minerals	2017	4,809,004	5	4
Spain	GVA, Coastal Tourism	2017	6,960,347,266	6960	4
France	GVA of living resources	2017	2,187,797,205	2188	4
France	GVA, Oil, gas, minerals	2017	8,382,364.769	8	4

France	GVA, Coastal Tourism	2017	8,099,650,466	8100	4
Portugal	GVA of living resources	2018	904,722,600	905	4
Portugal	GVA, Oil, gas, minerals	2018	2,362,200	2	4
Portugal	GVA, Coastal Tourism	2018	5,291,328,000	5291	4
England	Value of fish landings	2019	282,261,200	282	2
Scotland	Value of fish landings	2019	742,053,200	742	2
Wales	Value of fish landings	2019	20,435,200	20	2
Northern Ireland	Value of fish landings	2019	19,158,000	19	2
Isle of Man	Value of fish landings	2019	12,772,000	13	2
Guernsey	Value of fish landings	2019	7,663,200	8	2
Total UK	Value of fish landings	2019	1,084,342,800	1084	2
UK	Coastal tourism	2019	1,563,548,240	1564	10
UK	Offshore wind electricity generation	2018	378,434,360	378	10
UK	Offshore oil and gas	2019	8,355,442,400	8355	11
Canada	marine landings and aquaculture	2018	2,358,065,112	2358	5
Canada	Offshore oil and gas	2018p	3,487,877,928	3488	9
Canada	Coastal tourism and recreation	2018p	2,177,256,068	2177	9
US	Living resources contribution to GDP	2019	467,929,3241	4679	3
US	Tourism contribution to GDP	2019	74,843,137,168	74843	3
US	Minerals contribution to GDP	2019	561,356,054	561	3
Cayman Islands	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2019	3,370,881.72	3	1
Costa Rica	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2020	27,898,796.86	28	1
Bahamas	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2015	83,724,641.44	84	1
Barbados	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2019	3,055,500	3	1
Bermuda	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2019	5,565,000	6	1
British Virgin Islands	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2018	1,054,000	1	1
Saint Lucia	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2019	12,765,370	13	1
Trinidad and Tobago	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2018	15,146,987.65	15	1
Caribbean*	Value of living resources	2012	41,000,0000	410	6
Caribbean*	Offshore oil and Gas	2012	5,640,000,000	5640	6
Caribbean*	Coastal tourism	2012	4,710,000,0000	47100	6
Colombia	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2020	114,848,729.4	115	1
Guatemala	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2020	8,443,400	8	1
Guyana	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2019	53,611,046	54	1
Uruguay	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2020	32,170,430.23	32	1
Benin	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2019	93,364,328.35	93	1
Cabo Verde	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2020	11,015,455.18	11	1
Cameroon	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2019	125,725,200	126	1

Gambia	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2019	203,992,194.1	204	1
Ghana	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2019	443,709,242.2	444	1
Mauritania	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2012	112,715,133.8	113	1
Morocco	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2020	1,130,000,000	1130	12
Namibia	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2020	617,065,987.9	617	1
Nigeria	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2020	4,310,566,000	4311	1
Senegal	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2019	346,575,600	347	1
South Africa	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2018	253,627,000	254	13,14
South Africa	Tourism contribution to GDP	2018	249,297,000	249	13,14
South Africa	GVA offshore oil gas and mining	2018	106,248,000	106	13,14
Togo	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2019	47,300,800	47	1
Africa	GVA offshore oil and gas	2017	80,000,000,000	80000	8
Greenland	GVA fishing and aquaculture	2019	219,921,000	220	1

Notes: * : Anguilla, Antigua and Barbuda, Aruba, The Bahamas, Barbados, Belize, Bonaire, British Virgin Islands, Cayman Islands, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Curaçao, Dominica, the Dominican Republic, Grenada, Guadeloupe, Guatemala, Haiti, Honduras, Jamaica, Martinique, Mexico, Montserrat, Nicaragua, Panama, Puerto Rico, St. Barthelemy, St. Eustatius, St. Kitts and Nevis, St. Lucia, St. Maarten, St. Martin, St. Vincent and the Grenadines, Trinidad and Tobago, U.S. Virgin Islands, and República Bolivariana de Venezuela as reported by 6 Ref (last column):

1: UN data: Value added by industries at current prices

Source: National Accounts Official Country Data | United Nations Statistics Division GVA Fisheries. The Economic Statistics Branch of the United Nations Statistics Division (UNSD) maintains and updates the National Accounts Official Country Data database.

2: Marine Management Organisation. United Kingdom commercial sea fisheries landings by Exclusive Economic Zone of capture 2012-2019

3: Ocean Economy data, National Ocean Economics Program based on ENOW Ocean economy

4: EU Blue economy report 2020

5: Authors own estimates based on: OECD - ACQUACULTURE PRODUCTION

https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=FISH_FSE

OECD - MARINE LANDINGS https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=FISH_FSE and Impact estimates based on multipliers from Statistics Canada table 36-10-0595-01.

6: Patil, P.G., Virdin, J., Diez, S.M., Roberts, J., Singh, A. (2016). Toward A Blue Economy: A Promise for Sustainable Growth in the Caribbean; An Overview. The World Bank, Washington D.C.

8: UA-BIRA, 2019. Annexe 4. Énergie durable, ressources minérales et industries innovantes dans le contexte de l'économie bleue de l'Afrique. Nairobi, Kenya

9: Authors own calculations based on Government of Canada 2021, Canada's oceans and the economic contribution of marine sectors.

10: ONS: Tourism and outdoor leisure accounts, natural capital, UK: 2021 based on: Office for National Statistics, Great Britain Tourism Survey and Great Britain Day Visits Survey

11: ONS, Marine accounts, natural capital, UK: 2021

12: www.statista.com. The country total is attributed to the Atlantic fishery given the negligible share of Mediterranean captures.

13: The Eastern Cape Oceans Economy Strategic Roadmap (2019), "Ocean Economy in the Eastern Cape and South Africa, a Status quo and Baseline assessment", Province of the Eastern Cape Office of the Premier

14: SAT (2024), "Tourism performance report, January-March 2024"

To conclude, Figure 1 reports the share of value added originated by the marine ecosystem provisioning services, as they have been defined here, over the total country/regional value added. Keeping in mind the caveats from the method section, and, accordingly, the potentially low representativity of the numbers, this exercise is however useful to offer some comparisons across the orders of magnitude.

Figure 1: % GVA from Atlantic ecosystem provisioning services over total GVA⁽¹⁾ by country/region

Notes.

(1): Ratios have been computed using countries' current value GVA in the same years as indicated in Table 1. Source: World Bank Indicators available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.FCST.CN>

*: Includes living resources, oil gas and minerals, coastal tourism

°: includes just living resources (fish and aquaculture)

Caribbean includes Antigua and Barbuda, Aruba, The Bahamas, Barbados, Belize, British Virgin Islands, Cayman Islands, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Curaçao, Dominica, the Dominican Republic, Grenada, Guatemala, Haiti, Honduras, Jamaica, Mexico, Nicaragua, Panama, Puerto Rico, St. Kitts and Nevis, St. Lucia, St. Maarten, St. Vincent and the Grenadines, Trinidad and Tobago, and República Bolivariana de Venezuela

5 Evaluation of cultural services provided by iconic Atlantic marine sites

5.1 Background

Current ocean management systems have often not been able to deal with the global pressures that are undermining marine biodiversity (Cheung et al., 2009). In this context, marine protected areas (MPAs) have become one of the most used spatial management tools in the world to both reduce biodiversity loss and increase nature's contributions to people (NCP) (Ban et al., 2019). Crucial domains of ocean governance such as ocean literacy and cultural engagement with oceans require broader advancement than at present to encompass all segments of society, including policymakers, resource managers, and industry stakeholders to raise awareness among these audiences about contemporary and future ocean challenges (IOC-UNESCO 2024).

In this research, we focus on the conservation, and tourism and recreation sectors since it is increasingly well recognised that MPAs can deliver co-benefits to nature and people from all sectors of society derived from natural and cultural heritage values. For example, habitat or species protection can positively impact fish assemblages and contribute to associated health, wellbeing and economic impacts on residents (Aburto-Oropeza et al., 2011; Nowakowski et al., 2023). MPAs can deliver provisioning, regulating, cultural and supporting ecosystem services. Cultural services (the material and nonmaterial benefits that people obtain from ecosystems) can derive from protection of areas and practices associated with cultural, spiritual and historical heritage, provision of nature-based recreational activities (based on scenic beauty and emblematic species) and creation of opportunities for science and education (see Villasante et al., 2023 for examples). These services are known as nature's contributions to people for a good quality of life (NCP) whereby culture is recognised as mediating the relationships between people and NCP (IPBES 2019). NCP can include instrumental values (e.g. food and feed, energy, materials) and relational values (e.g. physical and experiential interactions with nature, symbolic meaning, inspiration; physical, mental emotional health; way of life; cultural identity, sense of place; social cohesion) (IPBES 2019).

However, the effectiveness of MPAs in achieving their socio-ecological objectives and delivering associated NCP differs between areas depending on the level of enforcement of MPA strategies and users' compliance with plans and policies within protected areas (Lopes et al. 2017; Hilborn et al. 2014). MPAs are increasing in both number and importance, in part resulting from the IUCN World Conservation Congress recommendation to protect 30% of marine habitats globally and at least 30% of the ocean by 2030 (IUCN 2016). Therefore, holistic, efficient and cost-effective evaluations of the effectiveness of MPAs are critical to ensure they are achieving their stated objectives for ocean health and human wellbeing.

Socio-cultural values refer to the different ways in which communities of people (e.g. regions, societies, sectors) perceive and value nature and its contributions to people (e.g. appreciation of natural beauty, importance of social interactions, and role of cultural heritage in enhancing visitor experiences) (Garcia Rodrigues et al., 2024). For example, tourists may value the existence of cetaceans in a specific area for the benefits they gain from experiencing them in the wild, whereas fishers may receive disbenefits from the presence of those cetaceans if they consume a target fisheries species. Hence, there is growing interest in understanding the availability of and people's preferences for different types of NCP to inform effective MPA

management. This includes the application of pluralistic methods of valuations focusing on social justice to reduce potential asymmetries in the access and use of areas and resources by different rights holders and stakeholders (Villasante et al., 2023). Additionally, the socio-cultural values that people hold for marine environments including protected areas are increasingly being considered in the development of more inclusive and effective MSP and ocean governance strategies that consider multiple values of nature (Ainsworth et al., 2019; Villasante et al., 2023).

Tourism can facilitate multiple benefits to visitors and residents of MPAs (e.g. recreational enjoyment; economic benefits; conservation awareness; funding for conservation; research and monitoring; cultural exchange and education) as well as disbenefits (e.g. habitat degradation; pollution; overfishing and disturbance of wildlife; crowding and habitat displacement; and cultural and social impacts leading to social and economic inequalities) (Pham 2020). The impacts of tourism on the marine environment can vary depending on management practices, regulations, and visitor awareness and responsibility, therefore sustainable tourism practices and effective management strategies are crucial to balance the positive and negative impacts of tourism on MPAs (Pham 2020).

Evaluating visitors' socio-cultural values for different NCP provided by MPAs is therefore a critical consideration for effective management and conservation (Garcia Rodrigues et al. 2024). To illustrate, managers of Australia's Great Barrier Reef found that as people's concerns about the declining health of the Reef increased, the region's scientific heritage value continued to grow (GBRMPA 2019).

Visitors to MPAs may hold various kinds of socio-cultural values for NCP. For example, people can: gain emotional and psychological benefits (Moyle 2022); derive cultural value from biodiversity conservation and the intrinsic value of preserving endangered species (Halkos 2017); prioritise natural attractiveness and perceive environmental quality and management differently based on personal characteristics, such as socio-economic status and cultural ties (Petrosillo 2007); hold different cultural values and beliefs about environmental responsibility which can influence visitor behaviour (Wynveen 2013); value aesthetic enjoyment and the opportunity for recreation and leisure activities that connect them to nature (Jobstvogt 2014); and value social relations, where interactions with other tourists and locals enhance the visitor experience, reflecting the social dimension of NCP (Pinheiro 2021; Carvache-Franco 2023).

Additionally, marine tourism sites which are not part of a protected area can offer experiences which provide a variety of benefits such as improved marine awareness and personal wellbeing and may be more popular and accessible to local populations and visitors than protected areas (Wyles 2014). Yet, a lack of formal management can make it difficult to monitor and evaluate ecosystem health and social wellbeing in these areas, meaning that the socio-cultural values held for NCP available in individual sites are often not well understood.

Understanding visitor socio-cultural values for NCP can inform management strategies and enhance visitor experiences (Petrosillo 2007; Lemmen 2023), influence conservation efforts indicating a need for effective communication strategies to improve awareness and compliance with reserve rules (Moritsch 2019; Moyle 2022) and shape policy and management decisions (Roberts 2020; Mann-Lang 2023). Public awareness and integration of perceptions into management strategies is necessary to balance the benefits of recreational visits with the protection of marine environments (Wyles 2014; Hawkins 2016).

Understanding how visitors perceive and interact with marine areas is essential, as this offers insights into the effectiveness of those areas in delivering NCP and enhancing user experiences. These perceptions are a valuable indicator of the area's social impact and success in engaging with the public (Garcia Rodrigues et al., 2022).

Traditional approaches to evaluating NCP (e.g. personal interviews), often require substantial resources and funding, posing a challenge for many regions. Addressing this, our study introduces an innovative, low-cost methodology by analysing Google Maps (<https://www.google.com/maps>) reviews to capture and analyse visitor perceptions of MPAs and iconic marine tourist sites throughout the Atlantic Ocean.

We explored the ways that visitors to different types of iconic marine sites (e.g. protected areas and tourism sites) distributed around Atlantic Ocean coastlines, islands and the high seas culturally engage with the ocean by analysing their Google Maps reviews about sites they have visited. Our objectives were to: a) identify which NCP were most frequently mentioned by reviewers of selected sites; b) highlight variability in socio-cultural values held for and use of NCP according to local contexts; c) understand reviewers' perceptions about the impacts of plastics on NCP; and d) map at risk and vulnerable hot spots due to climate, local human activity or anthropogenic impact. This information revealed people's awareness of, interactions with, and (dis)benefits received from natural and cultural oceanic features and the potential value of those features to the conservation and tourism and recreation sectors; and highlighted the extent, location and challenges regarding plastics and other threats in the Atlantic marine environment. Gathering public perceptions about iconic sites contributes vital information to help scientists and management authorities prioritise attention and resources to protect marine biodiversity and ecosystems and enhance visitors' experiences.

5.2 Methods

Site Selection

The IUCN defines a protected area as 'a clearly defined geographical space, recognised, dedicated and managed, through legal or other effective means, to achieve the long-term conservation of nature with associated ecosystem services and cultural values' (Verschuuren et al., 2021; p2). Marine protected areas are places in the ocean that receive protection to safeguard biodiversity from abatable threats and by definition prioritise the conservation of nature over other activities (e.g. resource extraction) (Grorud-Colvert et al., 2021). The term MPA can refer to a specific designation of protected area but can also be used as an umbrella term for an area of sea that is designated to protect marine habitats and species. In this report, we use MPA as an umbrella term to refer to all the protected areas in our study collectively and to distinguish them from tourism sites (non-protected areas).

Selection criteria for MPAs and tourism sites in this study included: 1) a geographic spread of sites to represent various biogeographic provinces and ecoregions throughout the Atlantic Ocean (Spalding et al. 2007); 2) comparable kinds of sites with high visitor traffic and formal management strategies (e.g. World Heritage Sites, marine national parks, popular marine tourism sites); 3) a minimum of 100 Google Maps reviews per site; 4) each site had a unique location tag to avoid misidentification in Google Maps reviews; 5) sites represented a range of different socio-ecological characteristics, stressors or drivers (e.g. affected by climate change, marine plastics, management strategies) to facilitate capturing a wide range of socio-cultural

values; 6) site selection was coordinated with AtlantECO project partners to identify sites of special interest within the region.

Data Acquisition

Google Maps reviews

In Google Maps, members of the public can write reviews of places they have visited, post photos or videos or leave information. The reviews are voluntary, unpaid, public, non-anonymised and moderated by Google to prevent policy violations (Google 2024).

The methodology of this research encompassed several layers of analysis. It began with the meticulous collection of review data from selected sites, followed by an extensive preprocessing stage that included tokenization, conversion to lowercase, and removal of non-essential elements like punctuation and numbers.

The initial phase of the study involved the collection of visitor reviews from Google Maps for 23 protected areas and tourism sites across different countries around the Atlantic Ocean. This process was meticulously conducted to ensure compliance with data use policies and maintain user privacy. Data collection was carried out manually by a team of five technicians. Each technician was assigned specific MPAs from the list, with the objective of downloading up to 300 unique reviews for each area.

The search and data downloading were conducted in Google's Guest mode using Tor browser version 13.0.9, always in private browsing mode. Proton VPN, pointing to Springfield, Missouri, USA, was used to encrypt web traffic and mask IP addresses, ensuring the integrity and confidentiality of the data collection process. A key aspect of the data collection was ensuring the uniformity of the language across all reviews. As Google Maps and Search automatically translate content to the device's default language, all comments were downloaded in English. This automatic translation feature ensured that the reviews, irrespective of their original language, were uniformly analysed in English, providing consistency in the data set.

Technicians accessed the Google Maps platform, navigated to the designated MPA pages, and manually recorded the reviews, ensuring first the anonymization of the user. This was followed by documenting the date of the review, the user's rating, and the full text of the comment. The data collection was structured to optimise efficiency and accuracy. Each technician was trained in the data collection protocol, which included guidelines on recording and organising data uniformly. The technicians spent approximately 2-3 hours per day over a period of four weeks to complete this task, ensuring a comprehensive dataset without compromising the quality of the collected information. The manual approach not only complied with the platform's terms of service but also provided an opportunity for the research team to engage closely with the data, potentially offering additional insights into user perceptions and sentiments.

Data analysis

Once the reviews were downloaded we removed a small number which were duplicates, nonsensical, or apparently did not relate to the site in question. Textual content of individual reviews was treated as qualitative data and each review was coded manually. We excluded from this content analysis any reviews which included a rating but no written comment (N/A).

To begin, we coded data to identify the range of pursuits available in each site. We grouped these activities by topic into activities and sorted them according to four types of cultural practices based on Fish et al (2016, p213):

- ‘Playing and exercising - activities of non-work leisure time involving informal and physical interactions between people and the natural environment. These may be sedentary, active, social and solitary such as walking, dog walking, climbing, running, cycling, sitting, looking, listening, picnicking or paddling;
- Creating and expressing - activities of non-work leisure time defined by the conscious construction of symbolic artefacts and processes. This may include solitary pursuits inspired by natural environment such as drawing, painting, photography, writing, poetry, as well as organised performances and participation in customs and rituals that draw on/reflect the natural environment in some way: music, drama and storytelling;
- Producing and caring - activities that span and blur both work/nonwork engagements with the natural environment. The multitude of environmental and land based professions are included in this category as are more informal physical conservation and management of features of natural environment: cultivating land for food production, fishing, environmental volunteering, citizen science, gardening and, participation in agri-environmental stewardship;
- Gathering and consuming - activities spanning passive and active engagements with the natural world and which occur in both work and non-work contexts, such as: consuming food and drink of local provenance, collecting wild food, fibre and ornaments, consuming non conversational media and genre about a place e.g. local art/ artefacts/popular media/performances’.

Next, we coded the reviews according to whether the remarks related positively or negatively to concepts described in one or more of the 10 Goals (including eight Sub-Goals) of the Ocean Health Index (<https://oceanhealthindex.org/goals/>). For example, this comment describes why the case study site Bahía de Dakhla is special to the person commenting: “Dakhla Bay is a very beautiful and touristic place”, and was coded positively as ‘Sense of place - Lasting Special Places’. In contrast, this comment about the same site “There are many dead fish in the water” was coded negatively as ‘Biodiversity - Species’ since it reflects a negative perception about the health of the fish population. The key coding concepts we employed for each OHI Goal are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Content analysis coding protocol

Ocean Health Index Goals and Sub-Goals	Goal overview	Key coding concepts
Artisanal Fishing Opportunities	This goal measures whether people who need to fish on a small, local scale have the opportunity to do so.	References to the activities of small-scale fisheries.
Biodiversity - Habitats	This goal describes how	References to the perceived

	successfully the richness and variety of marine life is being maintained around the world.	health of habitats based on quality, extent or abundance.
Biodiversity - Species		References to the perceived health of species based on quality, diversity or abundance.
Carbon Storage	This goal captures the ability of coastal habitats (mangrove, tidal marsh and seagrass ecosystems) to store carbon given the amount of carbon they store and their health.	References to the perceived health of mangrove, tidal marsh or seagrass ecosystems based on quality, extent or abundance.
Clean Waters	The Clean Water goal captures the degree to which local waters are unpolluted by human-made causes.	References to the perceived cleanliness of the ocean based on clarity or presence of non-natural items.
Coastal Protection	This goal aims to assess the amount of protection provided by marine and coastal habitats against flooding and erosion to coastal areas that people value, (e.g. uninhabited (parks, special places, etc.)).	References to features perceived to provide physical protection to coastal areas or about evidence of flooding or erosion.
Food Provision - Capture Fisheries	This goal assesses our ability to sustainably maximize wild-caught or farmed marine foods.	References to availability and quality of locally provenanced seafood for consumption.
Food Provision - Mariculture		
Livelihoods & Economies - Livelihoods	This goal measures the number and quality of jobs (Livelihoods) and the amount of revenue produced (Economies) from sustainable marine-related industries.	References to the quality of employment or economic conditions of local people.
Livelihoods & Economies - Economies		References to availability and quality of local businesses of interest to tourists or investment in site management or infrastructure.
Natural Products	This goal assesses how well countries are maximizing the sustainable harvest of non-food marine resources.	References to the quality and availability of non-food marine resources.
Sense of Place - Iconic Species	This goal describes how well we are preserving current and future access to the coastal and marine systems that people value as part of their cultural identity. For the	References to iconic marine plants and animals, based on characteristics such as charisma, notoriety or size.

Sense of Place - Lasting Special Places	global assessment, this is evaluated by determining the condition of iconic species (iconic species subgoal) and the protection of coastal regions (lasting special places subgoal).	References to the characteristics of a site that make it special to individuals, groups or communities.
Tourism & Recreation	Coastal and marine tourism is a vital part of a country's economy. This goal measures participation in sustainable tourism to coastal regions.	References to participation in tourism or recreational activities based on availability or quality of the site or services provided.

We then calculated the proportion of reviews for all sites overall and within each site that related to each Goal and Sub-Goal to identify the most prevalent themes. We also calculated the proportion of positive and negative ‘remarks’ made by reviewers in their reviews. Since each review potentially contained multiple remarks, these could be coded to different Goals or Sub-Goals and could contain both positive and negative elements. For example, in the following review for Dakhla: “*The site is superb, but the progression of plastic pollution is alarming*” the first clause was coded as a positive remark relating to Sense of Place - Lasting Special Places and the second clause as a negative remark relating to ‘clean site’.

Perceptions about the impacts of plastics on ecosystem services

To address our objective of understanding perceptions about the impacts of plastics on ecosystem services, we coded remarks which pertained to plastics in the ocean under the Clean Waters Goal. We also created a separate code ‘clean site’ under the Sense of Place - Lasting Special Places Sub-Goal to capture remarks pertaining to plastics on land (e.g. on beaches, in coastal villages).

Estimated revenue raised by case study sites

Finally, to understand how much revenue is generated by individual sites and by the case study sites overall, we searched official websites and online resources (e.g. newsletters, annual reports) linked to individual sites to extract the most recent data available on visitor numbers and entrance fees where applicable. Where prices ranged depending on visitor’s age, ethnicity (e.g. Brazilian national, foreign national) or duration/type of access, we calculated a minimum and maximum annual estimate of annual revenue. We then multiplied the visitor numbers by the cost of entry per site to calculate an estimated annual revenue for each site.

5.3 Results

We extracted 6,319 reviews from 23 case study sites situated on coastlines, islands and the high seas throughout the Atlantic Ocean. These sites represent eight provinces, 20 ecoregions, 19 countries and six designations: five designations were types of protected areas (World Heritage Area/UNESCO Man and Biosphere Reserve, Marine Protected Area, Ramsar Site, Natural Park and National Park) while the sixth was ‘tourism area’ (Figure 1; Table 2).

On average, the sites had 3,657 Google Map reviews each, with a maximum of 23,089 reviews (Parque Nacional Natural Tayrona) and a minimum of 127 (Skomer Island). Average visitor ratings on a scale of one to

five, where one equaled very poor and five equaled very good, ranged from a minimum of 4.2 (Bojo Beach and Cayos Miskitos y Franja Costera Inmediata) to a maximum of five (Parque Nacional Marinho de Abrolhos and Skomer Island) (Table 3). All except two of the tourism sites (Vikurfjara Black Sand Beach and Playa el Yaque) had some kind of management system in place for at least part of the site (e.g. management plan or board).

On average across the 23 sites, four in ten (44%) ratings were provided without a written review, resulting in 3,541 (56%) reviews being manually content analysed. Table 3 summarises the number of reviews downloaded overall, the proportion of reviews with a rating but no review and the number of reviews analysed per site.

Figure 1: Map of 23 case study sites. Dark blue icon = National Park; green = UNESCO World Heritage Site; brown = Ramsar site; orange = tourism site; teal = national natural park; yellow = other type of protected area. Numbers refer to site names (see Table 2).

Table 2: Selected socio-ecological characteristics of case study sites sorted according to ecoregion based on Spalding et al., (2007).

Province	Ecoregion	Case study country	Case study site name (abbreviation) and [number]*	Site designation	No. of reviews
2. Northern European Seas	20. South and West Iceland	Iceland	Vikurfjara Black Sand Beach (Vikurfjara) [1]	Tourism site	1,544
2. Northern European Seas	25. North Sea	Norway	Ytre Hvaler Nasjonalpark (Ytre) [2]	National Park	691
2. Northern European Seas	26. Celtic Seas	Great Britain	Skomer Island (Skomer) [3]	Marine Conservation Zone	127
3. Lusitanian	27. South European Atlantic Shelf	Spain	Parque Nacional Marítimo-Terrestre de las Islas Atlánticas de Galicia (Islas Atlánticas) [4]	National Maritime-Terrestrial Park	4,008
3. Lusitanian	27. South European Atlantic Shelf	Portugal	Parque Natural do Sudoeste Alentejano y Costa Vicentina (Alentejano) [5]	Natural Park	21,790
3. Lusitanian	28. Saharan Upwelling	Morocco	Bahía de Dakhla (Dakhla) [6]	Ramsar site	251
3. Lusitanian	29. Azores Canaries Madeira	Azores	Praia do Fogo (Fogo) [7]	Tourism site	1,455
5. Cold Temperate Northwest Atlantic	37. Gulf of St Lawrence - Eastern Scotian Shelf	Canada	Basin Head Provincial Park (Basin Head) [8]	Marine Protected Area	896

5. Cold Temperate Northwest Atlantic	40. Gulf of Maine/Bay of Fundy	USA	Cape Cod National Seashore (Cape Cod) [9]	National Park	3,861
12. Tropical Northwestern Atlantic	65. Greater Antilles	Cuba	Parque Nacional Ciénaga de Zapata (Zapata) [10]	Ramsar Site, Wetland of International Importance	156
12. Tropical Northwestern Atlantic	66. Southern Caribbean	Venezuela	Playa el Yaque (El Yaque) [11]	Tourism site	1,783
12. Tropical Northwestern Atlantic	67. Southwestern Caribbean	Colombia	Los Corales del Rosario y de San Bernardo (Rosario) [12]	National Natural Park	254
12. Tropical Northwestern Atlantic	67. Southwestern Caribbean	Colombia	Parque Nacional Natural Tayrona (Tayrona) [13]	National Natural Park	23,089
12. Tropical Northwestern Atlantic	67 Southwestern Caribbean	Nicaragua	Cayos Miskitos y Franja Costera Inmediata (Miskitos) [14]	Ramsar site, Wetland of International Importance	435
12. Tropical Northwestern Atlantic	68. Western Caribbean	México	Reserva de la Biósfera Sian Ka'an (Sian Ka'an) [15]	Ramsar Site, Wetland of International Importance	3,637
12. Tropical Northwestern Atlantic	69. Southern Gulf of Mexico	México	Laguna Madre y Delta del Río Bravo (Río Bravo) [16]	Flora and Fauna Protection Area	1,881

12. Tropical Northwestern Atlantic	70. Floridian	USA	Everglades National Park (Everglades) [17]	World Heritage Area / National Park	11,873
14. Tropical Southwestern Atlantic	74. Fernando de Noronha and Atoll das Rocas	Brazil	Parque Nacional Marinho de Fernando de Noronha (Noronha) [18]	World Heritage Area / Marine National Park	3,237
14. Tropical Southwestern Atlantic	76. Eastern Brazil	Brazil	Parque Nacional Marinho de Abrolhos (Abrolhos) [19]	Marine National Park	229
16. West African Transition	79. Cape Verde	Cabo Verde	Boa Vista (Boa Vista) [20]	Tourism site (with nature reserve)	619
17. Gulf of Guinea	82. Gulf of Guinea Upwelling	Ghana	Bojo Beach (Bojo) [21]	Tourism site (with Ramsar site)	902
48. Magellanic	184. North Patagonian Gulfs	Argentina	Península Valdés (Valdés) [22]	World Heritage Area (Natural or Mixed) / Provincial Protected Area	1,195
50. Benguela	190. Namib	Namibia	Skeleton Coast National Park (Skeleton Coast) [23]	National Park	187

Table 3: Summary of reviews downloaded and analysed, sorted from highest to lowest according to the average rating of reviews analysed.

Case study site name	Total no. of reviews downloaded	Average rating of reviews downloaded	No. of N/A reviews downloaded	% of N/A reviews	Average rating of N/A reviews	Total no. of reviews analysed excluding N/A	Average rating of reviews analysed excluding N/A
Víkurfjara Black Sand Beach	296	4.8	140	47	4.77	156	4.7
Ytre Hvaler Nasjonalpark	296	4.7	196	66	4.54	100	4.9
Skomer Island	135	4.9	40	30	4.82	95	4.9
Parque Nacional Marítimo-Terrestre de las Islas Atlánticas de Galicia	299	4.8	147	49	4.85	152	4.7
Parque Natural del Suroeste Alentejano y Costa Vicentina	300	4.8	211	70	4.76	89	4.8
Bahía de Dakhla	256	4.5	140	55	4.37	116	4.6
Praia do Fogo	300	4.8	167	56	4.75	133	4.8
Basin Head Provincial Park	300	4.8	124	41	4.79	176	4.8
Cape Cod National Seashore	300	4.8	0	0	NA	300	4.8
Parque Nacional Ciénaga de Zapata	157	4.3	87	55	4.04	70	4.6
Playa el Yaque	300	4.7	115	38	4.73	185	4.7

Corales del Rosario y de San Bernardo National Natural Park	279	4.7	140	50	4.72	139	4.8
Parque Nacional Natural Tayrona	299	4.7	155	52	4.81	144	4.5
Reserva Biológica Cayos Miskitos y Franja Costera Inmediata	293	4.2	174	59	4.03	119	4.4
Reserva de la Biósfera Sian Ka'an	297	4.5	102	34	4.75	195	4.4
Laguna Madre y Delta del Río Bravo	297	4.5	188	63	4.45	109	4.6
Everglades National Park	300	4.7	133	44	4.87	167	4.6
Parque Nacional Marinho de Fernando de Noronha	300	4.8	0	0	NA	300	4.8
Parque Nacional Marinho de Abrolhos	234	4.8	83	35	4.78	151	4.9
Boa Vista	299	4.7	138	46	4.62	161	4.8
Bojo Beach	300	4.1	117	39	4.23	183	4.1
Península Valdés	296	4.6	97	33	4.85	199	4.5
Skeleton Coast National Park	186	4.4	84	45	4.41	102	4.4
TOTAL	6319	Average 4.6	2778	44%	Average 4.6	3541	Average 4.7

Activities conducted at the case study sites

Reviews about the sites mentioned almost 80 different kinds of pursuits. We grouped these activities by topic into 18 activities and sorted them according to four types of cultural practices based on Fish et al (2016): ‘playing and exercising’ (12 themes; Figure 2); ‘producing and caring’ (3); ‘gathering and consuming’ (2); and ‘creating and expressing’ (1) (Figure 3). Reviews indicated that all except one site (Dakhla, 9 activities) offered between 10 and 16 activities. Everglades, Islas Atlánticas, Fernando de Noronha, Rosario, and Península Valdés were reported as offering the widest diversity of activities (16).

Based on the highest average percentage of reviews per activity across all sites, the most frequently reported activities included:

- enjoying the physical characteristics of the site (e.g. beach/island/dunes/nature) (average of 64% of reviews across all 23 sites; (the two sites with the highest percentages for each activity among all sites: Rosario 86%, Praia do Fogo 82%);
- watching/interacting with wildlife (11%; Skomer 68%, Everglades 38%);
- aesthetic appreciation of the site (e.g. view scenery/sunset/sunrise/stars/sea) (10%; Cape Cod 32%, Alentejano 27%);
- exploring on land (e.g. walk/hike/bike/horse/vehicle) (8%; Cape Cod 43%, Islas Atlánticas 27%);
- water-based activities (e.g. diving/games/fishing) (7%; Basin Head 21%, Abrolhos 19%)
- nourishing the body or soul/get away from it all (7%; Boa Vista 21%, Bojo Beach 17%, Víkurfjara 17%); and
- interacting with/appreciating the ocean and its climate from land (7%; Víkurfjara 24%, Praia do Fogo 19%).

The high average rating of sites (4.7 out of 5 overall) indicates that most reviewers in our sample were very satisfied with their visit. Three sites: Ytre Hvaler, Skomer and Abrolhos, received the highest average rating among all sites (4.9), while Bojo Beach received the lowest (4.1). For Ytre Hvaler, reviewers most frequently reported enjoying the physical characteristics of the site (78%), aesthetic appreciation for aspects of the site (10%), and interacting with/appreciating the ocean and its climate from land (8%). Reviewers who visited Skomer, most frequently reported watching/interacting with wildlife (68%), taking a boat trip (18%) and visiting/learning about cultural/natural heritage (11%). Visitors to Abrolhos most frequently mentioned enjoying the physical characteristics of the site (70%), watching/interacting with wildlife (20%) and water-based activities (especially diving) (19%). Reviewers of Bojo Beach most frequently reported enjoying the physical characteristics of the site (54%), nourishing the body/soul/getting away from it all (17%) and taking a boat trip (12%).

Figure 2: Cultural practices mentioned by reviewers as being conducted at individual sites involving ‘playing and exercising’ activities. Each activity is represented by the percentage of reviews for a site mentioning the activity; total percentages for each site can equal more than 100% since multiple activities were reported. Sites are shown in order of highest to lowest total percentages, indicating the frequency and variety of activities mentioned per site (N=3,541).

Figure 3: Cultural practices mentioned by reviewers as being conducted at individual sites involving ‘producing and caring’ (recognise [need for] environmental protection, visiting a protected area, working at the site); ‘gathering and consuming’ (enjoy a meal or drinks, collect/interact with natural objects); and ‘creating and expressing’ (photography) activities. Each activity is represented by the percentage of reviews for a site mentioning the activity. Sites are shown in order of highest to lowest total percentages, indicating the frequency and variety of activities mentioned per site (N=3,541).

Socio-cultural (dis)benefits received from case study sites

On average 90% of remarks within reviews for all sites were positive indicating that mostly benefits and few disbenefits were received which supports the average rating of 4.7 given by reviewers. The proportion of positive remarks reported varied between sites, with Ytre Hvaler (99%) Skomer (96%), Basin Head (96%), Zapata (95%), Rio Bravo (95%), Dakhla (95%), Boa Vista (95%) and Abrolhos (95%) being the sites that received the highest proportions of positive remarks. Bojo Beach (74%), and Tayrona (78%) received the least proportions of positive remarks.

The frequency with which reviewers reported (dis)benefits relating to the OHI Goals and Sub-Goals is shown in Figure 4. The most important Goals were: Sense of Place, Tourism & Recreation, Livelihoods & Economies, Biodiversity and Clean Waters, as well as 'clean site'. Reviewers reported different proportions and combinations of (dis)benefits for different sites reflecting the variation in socio-ecological characteristics of each site and quality of experiences delivered (Figures 5, 6).

The unequal distribution of (dis)benefits received across individual sites is further demonstrated in Figures 7 to 13, where sites are grouped according to the province in which they are situated to enable comparison by similar biogeographic characteristics. Examples of positive and negative reviews are also presented as text in Tables 4 to 11 in order of the most frequently mentioned benefits and disbenefits overall. The examples provided for each site are direct quotes and represent recurring themes for those sites.

Figure 4: Proportion of comments from all 23 sites combined coded according to the 10 OHI Goals/Sub-Goals and 'clean site'. Negative reviews = disbenefits received; positive reviews = benefits.

Figure 5: Comparison of case study sites, showing the percentage of positive reviews (benefits) which related to individual Goals/Sub-Goals for each site.

Figure 6: Comparison of case study sites, showing the percentage of negative reviews (disbenefits) which related to individual Goals/Sub-Goals for each site.

Figure 7: Northern European Seas.

Figure 8: Lusitanian.

Figure 9: Cold Temperate Northwest Atlantic.

Parque Nacional Ciénaga de Zapata

Playa el Yaque

Los Corales del Rosario y de San Bernardo

Parque Nacional Natural Tayrona

Figure 10: Tropical Northwestern Atlantic.

Figure 11: Tropical Southwestern Atlantic.

Figure 12: West African Transition and Gulf of Guinea.

Figure 13: Magellanic and Benguela.

Table 4: Sense of Place - Lasting Special Places

Name of site	% of reviews for site	Positive comments
Abrolhos	94	“The place is incredible: lots of beauty, lots of peace”
Alentejano	93	“Only to be seen to dream of the mysteries of nature”
Basin Head	93	“Beautiful beach. Love the squeaky sand!”
Cape Cod	91	“Gorgeous. Idyllic beach. Stunning and breathtaking. Every day. Every hour practically this beach has different colorings in the sky and sea. It’s always different and beautiful”
Fogo	91	“A vast wild beach at the foot of the mountains”

Name of site	% of reviews for site	Negative comments
Sian Ka’an	7	“Dissatisfaction with the Sian Ka’an Biosphere, to see the beaches full of the Sargasso seaweed is bad enough but to see the unending plastic, fishing nets and all sorts of rubbish in this what was a beautiful place and on top of that abandoned hotel collapsed into the ocean with its plastered walls breaking up into the sea and dozens of stainless steel water heater tanks left on the beach will make you cry, well it did me!”
Bojo	6	“Great place, good food and friendly staff unfortunately let down by litter strewn across the beach”
Islas Atlánticas	4	“It is not very quiet, nor idyllic as it is supposed to be, as everything is becoming overcrowded”
Vikurfjara	4	“There is black sand, but it is boring”

Table 5: Tourism & Recreation

Name of site	% of reviews for site	Positive comments
Cape Cod	87	“A great place to spend some time. Hiking, biking, swimming or just relaxing”
Everglades	72	“Was on my bucket list and the airboat ride was fantastic”
Skomer	69	“Lovely sunny day on a peaceful island. Stunning views and great to be so close to the wildlife”
Boa Vista	63	“Small island in Cape Verde that is definitely worth it for those looking for relaxation”
Basin Head	60	“The beach has so much to offer”

Name of site	% of reviews for site	Negative comments
Tayrona	20	“An unsatisfactory experience, a place for very young kids or people trained in tracking. The trails are in a terrible state, not only poorly marked, but also with strong rocky slopes and mud, which makes it impossible to appreciate the views”
Bojo	16	“They don't have a wash room on this Beach, the makeshift structure for convenience is a real daylight nightmare”
Sian Ka'an	14	“Definitely can be skipped. Especially the boat tour there, you might see a dolphin or turtle. But don't get close enough to land to see anything. If you go, definitely take the boat from Boca Paila and avoid the horrible drive there. Roads are horrible, my whole body was aching when we got home”
Everglades	10	“Disappointed! Tourist trap, expensive for what it is. Indeed, the only crocs seen were in the show, with a raccoon, and an albino croc”
Fernando de Noronha	10	“The place is beautiful, but with the amount charged for environmental fees, not having sanitation in seaside restaurants on more remote beaches is absurd. There is technology available today to do much better”

Table 6: Livelihoods & Economies - Economies

Name of site	% of reviews for site	Positive comments
Fogo	19	“There's a nice snack bar for drinks and ice cream”
Sian Ka'an	17	“It's wonderful. We took advantage of a complete pack for 159 per person. This includes travel from Playa del Carmen to Thulum”
Islas Atlánticas	14	“Very nice place, good food, and incredible views”
Skomer	13	“Amazing trip with Pembrokeshire Island trips to skomer island... Really informative and friendly crew”
Vikurfjara	13	“...plenty of diners and shops around. This is a good halfway point of traveling across the country”
Zapata	13	“Park is amazing, this wildlife refuge is well managed and protected”

Name of site	% of reviews for site	Negative comments
Fernando de Noronha	23	“Park could be better maintained. But we observed that improvements have been made. It is necessary to repair the ship that shows the seabed. The access roads are in a deplorable condition. Mud everywhere and holes in almost all access points”
Bojo	21	“This place is slowly dying. You pay GHC25 to get in and boat skippers begging for tips. Everything her is pricy. Rubbish is starting build up at the sea front and local fishermen selling fish at the beach”
Valdes	20	“I can't drive 10,000 km and be told that the road to see elephant seals is closed due to rain. I paid 10 euros to enter”
Tayrona	18	“Unique opportunity to be with nature. Cabo San Juan is expensive, everything is quite expensive”
Sian Ka'an	13	“Stunning price: 2200 MXN/person after negotiating. All excursions are the same no matter which agency you book with. In our van, we all went through different tours”

Table 7: Biodiversity - Species

Name of site	% of reviews for site	Positive comments
Skomer	39	“One of the most beautiful Wildlife Islands in the world: Manx Shearwaters, Puffins, Razorbills, Guillemots, Fulmars, Kittiwakes, Blackbacked Gulls, Guillemots, in fact an almost endless list of Northern Hemisphere Seabirds”
Abrolhos	17	“Spectacular marine life!!”
Everglades	16	“Saw a lot of wildlife during our 2hrs at the park!”
Sian Ka’an	14	“We had a great day and we were able to observe a lot of animals which was great! Nature and animals are really preserved and it’s great!!”
Valdes	14	“Península Valdés in Patagonia is a site of global significance for the conservation of marine mammals. It is home to an important breeding population of the endangered southern right whale as well as important breeding populations of southern elephant seals and southern sea lions. The orcas in this area have developed a unique hunting strategy to adapt to local coastal conditions”

Name of site	% of reviews for site	Negative comments
Fogo	5	"... (the beach) was covered in poisonous jellyfish when we went in April"
Sian Ka'an	4	"The snorkeling, on the other hand, was quite disappointing. A lot of coral is dead and there is a lot of seaweed"
Cape Cod	3	"Just download the Shark Alert app provided by the Atlantic White Shark Conservancy and keep your eyes peeled for large dark shapes in the water 😊!"
Basin Head	2	"It was very busy when we went and there were lots of jellyfish in the water and on the beach so not many people were swimming"
Everglades	2	"Somehow the only wild life we saw was this beautiful grasshopper and a Bald Eagle, however, it was not long after Hurricane Ian (I think). Still had a great trip and saw lots of stunning scenery! Can't control wildlife :)"
Islas Atlánticas	2	"Beware of the seagulls!! They are a bunch of bandits who steal your food without hesitation. It is better not to eat in the beach area"

Table 8: Sense of Place - Iconic Species

Name of site	% of reviews for site	Positive comments
Skomer	53	“Dream came true...surrounded by puffins !!”
Everglades	29	“Seeing alligators in their natural habitat was very cool. My husband loved it. I personally loved the manatees”
Valdes	20	“Along the route you can see whales, elephant seals and many other species in their natural habitat”
Zapata	20	“Amazing experience in the Las Salinas area where we could watch hundreds of pink flamingos as well as so many other species of birds fish and custacious. We even saw a wild dog, did not know they existed”
Abrolhos	16	“For marine life lovers, Abrolhos is a spectacle. Also excellent for diving, it is one of the biggest Brain Coral complexes! Between the months of July and October is the Humpback Whale season, so get ready to have beautiful surprises from these giants! It's perfect!”

Name of site	% of reviews for site	Negative comments
Everglades	4	“Scam! + 1 hour outbound bus, + 1 hour return bus from Miami, for 35 minutes by boat with 10 other boats at the same time, same route. Just from the noise, we quickly tell ourselves that we won't see any alligators”
Valdes	3	“If it's not whale season, move on, you'll save your time and money. Go to Punta Delgada, you will see colonies of fur seals, noys they say. Perfect, rejoices the tourist before coming across a sign which prohibits you from passing in the name of the sacred right to private property... So much the worse for the 80 km of terrifyingly monotonous track... Rusty signs sternly order you to stay in your vehicle... We arrive, it's very beautiful, a beach full of moving brown dots on black sand, elephant seals, numerous, harems, small ones, it's very nice but very distant and you can only observe them from a rickety and overcrowded footbridge. All that remains is for us to face the hundred kilometers of flat gravel to return because, of course, access to the fabulous estancia was just as forbidden, cerrado and prohibido as in the south. A total scam”
Abrolhos	1	“Wonderful diving! But for those who want to see whales ?? check the calendar?????. It's not all year round”

Sian Ka'an	1	"The reserve is magnificent but there is a small downside regarding the organized outings where you find 15 boats crowded around 3 poor dolphins"
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Table 9: Biodiversity - Habitats

Name of site	% of reviews for site	Positive comments
Fernando de Noronha	14	"Environmental preservation is also very evident and everyone takes great care to preserve the place. Although it's not cheap, I highly recommend it to anyone who can plan to visit. The expression that traveling makes us richer really makes sense here. Big hug to all!"
Alentejano	12	"Natural coasts of wild beauty, difficult to describe, the multicolored landscapes are wonderful to visit!!"
Abrolhos	11	"It's an incredible place to dive and enjoy nature. Beautiful. Fauna and flora untouched by man and protected by the Brazilian navy. Truly incredible place, with the most beautiful blue waters I have ever seen"
Sian Ka'an	13	"The Sian Ka'an Biosphere Reserve is the largest protected area in the Mexican Caribbean, it is nature in its purest form"
Zapata	13	"UNESCO declared it a biosphere reserve in 2001. It is home to the largest wetland in the entire Caribbean... There are 14 types of vegetation on the surface, such as mangrove forest, terrestrial forest, cactus, savanna and jungle"

Name of site	% of reviews for site	Negative comments
Alentejano	1	"Beautiful landscape, unfortunately you can currently see some burnt trees"
Everglades	1	"All trees dead. Sad beetle destroyed them looks like huge fire no living trees as far as eye can see. Drove from Naples to Miami"
Islas Atlánticas	1	"Incredible eucalyptus, beach loaded with pleasure boats and gas station restoration"

Table 10: Clean site

Name of site	% of reviews for site	Positive comments
Bojo	13	“I have been taking guests to Bojo Beach for about 7 years because it is the cleanest beach in the area”
Rio Bravo	6	“The beach is beautiful and very clean, a place to find peace”
Fogo	5	“When we were there, the beach was also being cleaned, which I think is great”
Islas Atlánticas	4	“Well cared for and very friendly people. Great idea to not have trash cans and let people take their trash”

Name of site	% of reviews for site	Negative comments
Sian Ka’an	6	“THE DR SIAN KAAAN BIOSPHERE GARBAGE DUMP, beaches full of garbage, with almost no access to the sea, only houses and private properties with expensive beach clubs. A place forgotten by the government but good for charging entry because it is a national park”
Bojo	5	“I feel bad about this review but my time and money were wasted because of how dirty the beach was. I have to be honest it used not to be like this. Standard have clearly fallen”
Dakhla	2	“The site is superb, but the progression of plastic pollution is alarming”
Fernando de Noronha	2	“The government invests very little in basic sanitation despite the exorbitant fee it charges, some beaches are polluted and have a constant bad smell: Boldró, do Cachorro and Sueste”

Table 11: Clean Waters

Name of site	% of reviews for site	Positive comments
Islas Atlánticas	9	“Incredible place, where the white sand contrasts with the crystal blue waters”
Basin Head	7	“Without doubt It's the most beautiful beache in PEI (Prince Edward Island)! I was mesmerized by the bright sand and clear turquoise water”
Rosario	6	“Excellent place, highly recommended. A super crystal clear sea and delicious food and the best thing is the journey that is experienced when passing the entire Gulf of Morrosquillo”
El Yaque	3	“Beach with serene and crystalline waters”
Abrolhos	3	“Exuberant biodiversity and crystal clear waters, a paradise that deserves to be preserved”

Name of site	% of reviews for site	Negative comments
Bojo	2	“If you don't mind paying 30 GHC to enter and another 20 GHC for a lounge chair, the filthy plastic washing out of the sea and just want to sit, then, this is an okay place to go”
Fogo	1	“Waters a little polluted with sticks and feathers”
Sian Ka'an	1	“The Mexican government are happy to make tourists pay \$105 pesos to get into the park and not do anything to keep this once great place as nature intended. The Sargasso seaweed can almost be considered a natural disaster but even that is debatable because the pollutant's from farming coming down the rivers from the USA, Brazil and others are probably causing this problem!”

Perceptions about the impacts of plastics on ecosystem services

Our analysis identified several comments that expressed perceptions about the impacts of plastics on cultural services. These mainly related to the presence of plastics spoiling reviewers' recreational activities such as enjoying scenic beauty (aesthetic appreciation). These plastics were sometimes said to be found in the ocean (Clean Waters) but were mostly described as being on beaches or nearby areas (Sense of Place - Lasting Special Places: clean site).

Clean Waters

Bojo received specific negative remarks from three reviewers about the impacts of plastics in the ocean. These reviewers appeared to experience the plastics from land indicating that the plastics were very close to the shore. Their remarks referred to the plastics spoiling the aesthetic appeal of the site, inferred a lack of desire to enter the polluted water, and pointed to a lack of effective management of the plastics by site authorities. To illustrate:

“If you don't mind paying 30 GHC to enter and another 20 GHC for a lounge chair, the filthy plastic washing out of the sea and just want to sit, then, this is an okay place to go” (Bojo).

“Fantastic beach only criticism is how much waste washed up on the beach and how it was dealt with - stop burying the waste in 2inch of sand on the beach by the water line” (Bojo).

Sense of Place - Lasting Special Places: Clean site

Ten sites received negative remarks about the impacts of plastics on land (e.g. on the beach or land nearby): Sian Ka'an (14); Bojo (8); Boa Vista (2); Dakhla (2); Rosario (2); Tayrona (2); Cape Cod (1), Fernando de Noronha (1); Rio Bravo (1); Valdes (1).

Reviewers of these ten sites claimed to see all kinds of plastic litter strewn on walking trails, across beaches, on the fences of private properties near the site or in wildlife breeding areas. The remarks tended to express disgust, sadness, disappointment or anger at the sight of plastic litter in the marine environments visited, seemingly due to the sharp contrast of the unsightly litter with the natural beauty of the location. In some cases (e.g. on beaches), the reviewers blamed local sources for the litter (e.g. from nearby human habitation or fishing activities) (e.g. Boa Vista, Bojo, Cape Cod, Dakhla, Rio Bravo, Sian Ka'an, Valdes), while in others reviewers blamed tourists for leaving litter on walking trails (e.g. Fernando de Noronha, Tayrona). One example demonstrates a potential conflict in Rosario between local residents and tourists: a reviewer described how a restaurant waiter blamed tourists for the amount of litter on the beach, but as he was cleaning their table the waiter threw plastic litter onto the sand that the reviewer claimed “a couple had taken out of the sea”. This reviewer also complained about the lack of care for the local natural resources:

“...when you walk around their houses it is a dunghill, when you go snorkeling the boatman drops anchor on top of the coral, people step on the coral, obviously the vast majority are dead and On the island of Tintipán there are lots and lots of dead corals on its coast, a paradise turned into a dunghill, learn from Caño Cristales and its management as a Park” (Rosario).

Ten of the Sian Ka'an reviewers complained about having paid a substantial amount of money either to enter the biosphere reserve or for a guided tour but after experiencing the amount of litter in the area they described feeling that the revenue derived from these fees was not being invested by local authorities to manage the litter problem. One reviewer described having volunteered in a beach clean up to gather plastic litter in the reserve. To illustrate:

“Clearly none of the entrance fee (105 peso pp) is going towards repairing facilities/roads or litter picking. Complete waste of time...litter is EVERYWHERE - the beach is disgusting with litter all over the place. Expected more for a protected area... Better to spend your time in a national park where money is spent actually conserving it, rather than leaving fishing nets and broken beer bottles strewn all over the beach” (Sian Ka'an reviewer #1).

“The Mexican government are happy to make tourists pay \$105 pesos to get into the park and not do anything to keep this once great place as nature intended. But it is time to call a halt to creating new plastics and make existing plastics a valuable commodity so it is worthwhile to be collected from the beaches. Whilst governments of countries do not say “Not in my backyard “ this is just going to carry on! The Loggerhead turtles in the Sian Kaan are having a difficult job digging through the rubbish and sand to lay their eggs. Goodness only knows what damage it is doing in this reserve and the rest of the world” (Sian Ka'an reviewer #2).

“Today 22 April 2023 it was world's earth day and we did a beach clean up in the Reserva Sian Ka'an. We first stopped at the narrowest part, where at one side was the mangrove and at the other side the sea & beach. Here we saw a crocodile and a manatee. As all volunteers came together we went to the actual place where the clean up was. There were a lot of volunteers participating. We went with 7 persons of Infinity2 diving from Tulum. We gathered all together a lot of plastic garbage” (Sian Ka'an reviewer #3).

In Boa Vista, two reviewers inferred there is significant plastic pollution on land, expressing sympathy with the local community regarding the impacts of plastics on the local marine environment and pointing to the potential role of responsible tourism to help manage the litter problem:

“Unfortunately, there are so many abandoned and ruined buildings and resorts that disfigure the landscape, and just as much rubbish around the island... It is certainly a destination that is far behind in terms of issues such as conscious tourism and sustainability, but it is certainly not only the fault of the inhabitants” (Boa Vista reviewer #1).

“For a small island, Cape Verde has some of the most breathtaking beaches. Its a place of outstanding beauty. Visitors should help preserve this ecosystem my volunteering to do environmental clean up” (Boa Vista reviewer #2).

Mapping at risk and vulnerable hot spots due to climate, local human activity or anthropogenic impacts

Our analysis revealed that 18 of the 23 iconic sites studied were facing socio-environmental threats at the time of our analysis which were significantly impactful for multiple reviewers to notice and mention in their reviews. These 18 sites were distributed around several biogeographic provinces of the Atlantic Ocean: Lusitanian (4 sites), Cold Temperate Northwest Atlantic (2), Tropical Northwestern Atlantic (7), Tropical Southwestern Atlantic (1), West African Transition (1), Gulf of Guinea (1), and Magellanic (1) (Figure 14). The five sites which did not receive remarks about such threats, included Northern European Seas (3 sites), the Tropical Northwestern Atlantic (1) and Benguela (1).

The threats reported can be categorised as being caused by local human activities (e.g. overcrowding of people on sites, lack of investment in site infrastructure, presence of plastics and other marine litter on land). However, we identified additional threats that could have a broad geographic range and can be designated as anthropogenic impacts (e.g. presence of plastics and other marine litter arriving from / in the ocean) or that could be caused by changes to the climate (e.g. potential blooms of undesirable species such as jellyfish or mosquitoes). Reviews highlighted that over half of the sites (13) were perceived as suffering from multiple kinds of threats, with El Yaque, Fernando de Noronha and Sian Ka'an being particularly adversely affected by six or more threats each. Reviews for the remaining sites (e.g. Abrolhos, Alentejano, Basin Head, Boa Vista, Bojo Beach, Cape Cod, Fogo, Islas Atlánticas, Miskitos, Rio Bravo, Tayrona, Valdes) mentioned only a few threats per site however those threats may still have serious local impacts (Table 12). Our analysis suggests these 20 sites may be at risk or vulnerable hotspots now or in the near future. Reviews we collected for Skeleton Coast, Skomer, Víkurfjara, Ytre Hvaler and Zapata did not mention similar threats.

Figure 14: Map of at risk or vulnerable sites. Dark blue icon = National Park; green = UNESCO World Heritage Site; brown = Ramsar site; orange = tourism site; teal = national natural park; yellow = other type of protected area. Numbers refer to site names (see Table 2).

Table 12: Key threats mentioned by reviewers.

Case study site name	Key threats										
	Local human activities								Anthropogenic impacts	Climate impacts	
	Overcrowding of people in the site	Lack of investment in site infrastructure	Presence of plastics and other litter on land	Site not contributing effectively to social equity in local community	Site not adequately managed for biodiversity	Site is not adequately managed for tourism	Biodiversity negatively affected by tourism	Biodiversity negatively affected by plastics	Presence of plastics and other litter arriving from / in ocean	Potential blooms in undesirable species	Biodiversity affected by climate change events
Parque Nacional Marinho de Abrolhos		Yes									
Parque Natural do Sudoeste Alentejan		Yes			Yes						

o y Costa Vicentina											
Basin Head Provincial Park	Yes									Yes	
Boa Vista				Yes							
Bojo Beach		Yes	Yes	Yes							
Cape Cod National Seashore	Yes		Yes			Yes					
Bahía de Dakhla	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes						
Playa el Yaque	Yes	Yes		Yes		Yes			Yes	Yes	
Everglades National Park					Yes	Yes	Yes			Yes	Yes

Parque Nacional Marinho de Fernando de Noronha	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes			Yes	Yes	
Praia do Fogo										Yes	
Parque Nacional Marítimo-Terrestre de las Islas Atlánticas de Galicia	Yes									Yes	
Cayos Miskitos y Franja Costera Inmediata					Yes						
Laguna Madre y		Yes	Yes								

Delta del Río Bravo											
Los Corales del Rosario y de San Bernardo	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes					
Reserva de la Biósfera Sian Ka'an		Yes	Yes		Yes		Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes
Parque Nacional Natural Tayrona	Yes					Yes					
Península Valdés	Yes										
TOTAL number of sites affected	9	9	7	4	6	6	2	1	2	7	2

Estimated revenue raised by case study sites

Online searches revealed visitor data and entrance fees for 11 of the 23 case study sites. For a further six sites we were only able to find estimated visitor numbers. For the remaining six sites we found neither visitor data nor entrance fees (Table 13).

We therefore calculated an estimated annual revenue for 11 sites. In six of these cases, the entrance fees ranged in price depending on the type of visitor (e.g. based on age, type of activity or citizenship status), therefore we calculated an estimated minimum and maximum annual revenue. Thus, we calculated a lower total estimate of over US\$76 million and an upper estimate of almost US\$207 million in visitor revenue raised per annum. Sources of data are provided in Appendix Table S1.

Table 13: Estimated visitor revenue raised by case study sites estimated by annual visitor numbers and entrance fees (see Table S1 for sources of entrance fee and visitor number data).

Case study site name	Entrance fee	Estimated annual visitor numbers	Minimum annual revenue (US\$)	Maximum annual revenue (US\$)
Víkurfjara Black Sand Beach	0	Unknown	0	0
Ytre Hvaler Nasjonalpark	0	Unknown	0	0
Skomer Island	38-57	20,000 (2023)	760,000	1,140,000
Parque Nacional Marítimo-Terrestre de las Islas Atlánticas de Galicia	0	515,000 (2023)	0	0
Parque Natural do Sudoeste Alentejano y Costa Vicentina	0	13,303 (2017)	0	0
Bahía de Dakhla	0	90,000 (2021)	0	0
Praia do Fogo	0	112,000 (estimate)	0	0
Basin Head Provincial Park	0	75,000 (undated)	0	0

Cape Cod National Seashore	13-24€	4,000,000 (2023)	52,000,000	96,000,000
Parque Nacional Ciénaga de Zapata	0	275,000 (2016)	0	0
Playa el Yaque	0	Unknown	0	0
Los Corales del Rosario y de San Bernardo	2.71	530,127 (2021)	N/A	1,431,342
Parque Nacional Natural Tayrona	5-22	395,173 (2021)	1,975,865	8,693,806
Cayos Miskitos y Franja Costera Inmediata	0	Unknown	0	0
Reserva de la Biósfera Sian Ka'an	2.80	200,000 (2018)	N/A	560,000
Laguna Madre y Delta del Río Bravo	2.30	15,000 (undated)	N/A	34,500
Everglades National Park	18-24	1,000,000 (2023)	18,000,000	24,000,000
Parque Nacional Marinho de Fernando de Noronha	34-67	114,000 (2019)	3,876,000	7,638,000

Parque Nacional Marinho de Abrolhos	1.60-18	8,000 (2019)	12,800	144,000
Boa Vista	0	190,000 (undated)	0	0
Bojo Beach	1.60	unknown	0	0
Península Valdés	0-22	323,488 (2022)	0	67,116,736
Skeleton Coast National Park	1-5	800 annual limit	0	4,000
TOTAL (US\$)			76,624,665	206,762,384

5.4 Discussion

Overall, 90% of the Google Maps reviews analysed contained positive remarks about the case study sites in question. This finding accords with the high ratings reviewers awarded to each of the case study sites on the Google Maps reviews website and indicates high levels of visitor satisfaction among reviewers regarding their experiences of the sites.

The themes mentioned in reviewers' positive remarks highlight the importance of the OHI Goals and Sub-Goals: Sense of Place - places, Sense of Place – species, Tourism & Recreation, Livelihoods & Economies - economies, Biodiversity – species; Biodiversity – habitats, Clean Waters and the additional code 'clean site'. This result could support future Ocean Health Index assessments of individual case study sites or broader regional assessments. Cultural benefits such as sense of place, aesthetic pleasure and cultural identity associated with charismatic marine life and biodiversity have been found elsewhere to contribute to a 'fulfilled human life' demonstrating how high-quality nature-based experiences in marine settings can contribute to social wellbeing (Ainsworth et al. 2019).

More specifically, positive comments generally related to socio-cultural benefits such as the aesthetics and cleanliness of the marine environment, mysteries of nature, appreciation of vast wildernesses, ability to explore and experiment, opportunities to find isolation or to spend time in the company of friends or family members, enjoying good food, interacting with diverse and abundant species of wildlife, achieving one's dreams, engaging with local people, and experiencing healthy, well-preserved nature. Reviewers mentioned almost 80 different types of recreational activities they could conduct across the sites, most of which related to playing and exercising, indicating that reviewers mostly visited for recreational purposes. Reviewers particularly mentioned enjoying the physical and aesthetic characteristics of sites and watching or interacting with wildlife.

These findings support understanding of the major values for conservation of nature associated with NCP for the case study sites in general and for each site in particular which can provide a benchmark for the sound design and planning of their conservation management. Demonstrated conservation of natural and cultural values and NCP are considered criteria for achieving successful long-term conservation outcomes (IUCN & WCPA 2017).

The likely related expenditure in associated local businesses (e.g. guided tours, accommodation, meals, recreational gear) suggests the potential for significant economic effects in local economies. Some activities (e.g. aesthetic appreciation) might involve small contributions to local businesses (e.g. parking fees, refreshments) while others (e.g. stay overnight/vacation, boat trip, water-based activities) might require more significant knock on effects (e.g. equipment and/or vehicle hire, meals, accommodation) suggesting that each site offers a different economic potential and financial portfolio to local economies based on the types of experiences available and activities that can be conducted.

However, 10% of reviews were composed of negative remarks and reviewers identified various disbenefits received from the sites including: experiencing overcrowding of tourists, presence of marine litter on land and in the ocean, unsatisfying wildlife interactions, degraded environments, poor infrastructure or services, and high entrance fees. In fact, visitors themselves can contribute to degradation of marine environments as a result of conducting activities such as walking or rockpooling (Wyles et al., 2014). Also, some reviewers

complained that they thought entry fees to specific sites (e.g. Reserva de la Biósfera Sian Ka'an) were not being appropriately invested by park authorities in site management, especially regarding poor infrastructure (e.g. badly degraded roads or hiking trails, lack of sanitary facilities, mismanagement of waste) or marine litter / pollution. Additionally, entrance fees to some sites and associated costs for accommodation and meals were described as excessive (e.g. Fernando de Noronha) making access to such places exclusive to wealthier visitors and raising important questions around the equity of access to some MPAs.

Critically, the presence of marine litter is known to negatively affect the aesthetic and restorative quality of visitor experiences and impact detrimentally on recreational activities and beach enjoyment (UNEP 2021; Wyles et al. 2015). The presence of marine litter is also linked to reduced visitor satisfaction and likelihood of return visits, especially for first-time visitors (Schuhmann, 2012), declines in coastal tourism and losses of revenue since people tend to avoid sites if they are anticipated to be littered (UNEP 2021; Wyles et al., 2015).

Recent estimates of the amount of plastics in the oceans range between 75 – 199 million tons with estimates predicted to rise as high as 53 million tons per year by 2030 in a business as usual scenario (UNEP 2021). Plastics cause lethal and sub-lethal effects in many kinds of marine life from the largest mammals to the smallest invertebrates and can also alter global carbon cycling especially when major carbon sequestering marine ecosystems such as mangroves, seagrasses, corals and salt marshes are damaged (UNEP 2021). It is estimated that more than half of mangrove habitat globally is within 20 km of a river that discharges more than 1 ton per year of plastic pollution into the ocean, while seagrass, salt marsh and coral reef habitats are also badly affected (Harris et al. 2021).

Our investigation found that the presence of plastics in protected and non-protected marine tourism sites was a significant disbenefit to site reviewers regarding Sense of Place, Clean Waters and 'clean site', demonstrating the interlinked nature of these three concepts, and how the presence of plastics can negatively impact on the appeal of special places to people. Many reviewers expressed sadness, anger, grief and disappointment in their remarks about experiencing litter (e.g. 'filthy', 'dunghill') in places they otherwise considered beautiful and clean. The strength of feeling conveyed could be partly explained by the considerable physical, financial, time and emotional investment that visitors to the case study sites must have made (e.g. choosing where to invest limited vacation time and resources, travel time and costs, effort to reach remote destinations, entrance and accommodation fees, etc.). It could also be partly explained by loss of place attachment (solastalgia) – for example the idea of visiting a pristine marine environment compared with the reality of encountering a littered place, or from experiencing negative environmental changes in a familiar, beloved place leading to feeling distress and an inability to derive solace from that place (Phillips & Murphy 2021). Reviewers' strongly negative remarks about marine litter and lack of investment in site infrastructure and litter management could also indicate a negative feedback loop: increasing amounts of plastic pollution become increasingly more expensive to manage while the tourism revenue available to manage local litter decreases due to tourists avoiding sites.

In our study, seven sites were identified as being threatened by the presence of significant amounts of plastics and other litter on land (Bojo Beach, Cape Cod, Dakhla, Rio Bravo, Rosario, Sian Ka'an), the presence of plastics and other litter arriving from the ocean (Playa el Yaque), or the presence of plastics from both sources (Fernando de Noronha).

As an example, Bojo Beach received the largest number of critical comments both regarding the presence of plastics in the water and on shore, and for the way these plastics were perceived by some to be ‘managed’ (e.g. being buried in sand by the water line).

Bojo Beach is situated within the Densu Delta Ramsar Site, a Key Biodiversity Area, consisting of the urban riverine system of the Densu River (Key Biodiversity Areas Partnership 2024; Ramsar 2024). The Densu River traverses several towns and is widely polluted with microplastics (Blankson et al., 2022). Bojo Beach is also 12km north along the coast from Korle Lagoon at the mouth of the River Odaw - a wetland site that hosts Agbogbloshie slum, one of the world’s largest electronic dumping sites and one of the world’s most polluted wastelands (Airbus Intelligence 2024). Ghana is reported as importing approximately 215,000 tons of used consumer electronics from Western Europe annually and it is estimated that 250,000 tons of plastic waste from Ghana are dumped into the Atlantic Ocean annually (World Bank 2020; EcoHubMap 2024).

For Ghana, like many countries, managing plastic pollution is a major challenge due to significant population growth and urbanisation, shifts in lifestyle and consumption patterns and improper disposal of plastic waste coupled with limited resources for waste management infrastructure, poor enforcement of regulations and lack of public awareness and involvement (Awewomom et al., 2024). In fact, Ghana’s Ocean Health Index scores for Sense of Place (34 out of 100) and Clean Waters (33) are well below the global averages of 63 and 70 respectively (where a maximum of 100 represents the ideal situation) (<https://oceanhealthindex.org/regions/ghana/>). Research conducted with visitors to two beaches in Accra near Bojo Beach found that improved visual appeal and cleanliness of the beach environment, along with its natural features and availability of amenities and services, significantly contributed to enhance visitors’ overall perception and enjoyment of their beach experiences, and vice versa (Dzitse et al., 2024).

Even in Cape Cod National Seashore – which is notable in our research for the high proportion of positive reviews appreciating Sense of Place – places, the National Park Service acknowledges that marine debris ranging from single-use plastics to fishing gear is a problem at the site. As part of an educational strategy in conjunction with the national NOAA Marine Debris Program, the Park Service includes information on their website regarding the types and risks of marine debris and microplastics present and encourages visitors to the site to participate in beach clean-ups in their areas and to reconsider use of single-use plastics (Cape Cod National Seashore 2024).

We categorised 18 of our 23 case study sites as at risk or vulnerable hotspots due to being perceived by reviewers as suffering from various threats due to climate, local human activity or anthropogenic activities. At most sites, threats were multiple and potentially cumulative, and sites were distributed across a large geographic scale around coastlines, islands and high seas. Although threats were not mentioned in five sites pertaining to Northern European Seas, the Tropical Northwestern Atlantic and Benguela, we cannot discount their presence since they may have been mentioned in reviews we did not analyse.

Our results provide important social data on visitor perceptions that contribute to current understanding of the sites in question. For example, of all the at risk and vulnerable sites identified, reviewers’ remarks revealed that Sian Ka’an Biosphere Reserve, a World Heritage Site in Mexico, was vulnerable to the largest number of threats including: lack of investment in infrastructure (e.g. very poor quality road into the site), presence of plastics and other litter on land, the site is not adequately managed for biodiversity, biodiversity is negatively affected by tourism (e.g. large numbers of tourism boats closely crowding dolphins) and plastics (e.g.

loggerhead turtle nesting sites covered in rubbish), there are potential blooms in undesirable species (e.g. sargassum) and biodiversity may be affected by climate change events (e.g. dead coral).

These findings correlate with the IUCN's most recent assessment of this site which describes how 'Despite an overall good state of the World Heritage values related to natural beauty, there is a concern with respect to the coastal zone, which is affected by uncontrolled development and plastic debris' (IUCN 2020). Furthermore, the 'massive seasonal influx' of sargassum is considered a low threat but is becoming a serious threat to the site. The assessment reports that the site suffers from a large number of 'high threats' of major concern including the decline of coral cover which is considered to be due to 'a synergy of different drivers including bleaching events coupled with disease outbreaks, severe hurricane damage and anthropogenic stressors' and coastal development, mostly related to tourism (IUCN 2020). In accordance with the perceptions of reviewers regarding little reinvestment of fees into site management, the IUCN assessment acknowledges that site management has little influence on the broader developments resulting from the direct and indirect impacts of mass tourism along a massively transformed coastline (IUCN 2020).

El Parque Nacional Natural Los Corales del Rosario y de San Bernardo (aka Rosario) is a national natural park in Columbia which hosts more than 70% of the Colombian continental Caribbean coral reefs, as well as other important ecosystems such as seagrass meadows, mangroves, coastal lagoons, rocky coastline and sandy beach coastline (Henao-Castro et al., 2023). Recreational diving in the coral reefs was estimated to generate revenue of nearly US\$700,000 based on 2011 diver numbers (Trujillo et al., 2017).

However, our research identified five types of threats: overcrowding of people on the site, lack of investment in site infrastructure, presence of plastics and other litter on land, the site is not adequately managed for biodiversity and biodiversity is affected by tourism. We also reported that in 2021, over 530,000 visitors were recorded as having entered the park.

Park authorities in Rosario previously prioritised the problem of inadequate management and disposal of solid plastic waste in sandy beach ecosystems. Since 2010 authorities have been implementing regular beach clean-up events which are demonstrated to have raised awareness and sensitivity among participants about the importance of caring for the beach and oceans (Henao-Castro et al. 2023). Recent research has also detected that up to 70% of the most common microplastic residues on the park's beaches (including those islands most frequently visited by tourists) comes from synthetic clothing fibres and fragments of single-use plastics. Zooplankton are reported as mistakenly consuming these lethal microplastics thus affecting the entire food chain (Correa Rodriguez 2023). Subsequently, an educational strategy was implemented with community members in the national park to assess knowledge and behaviours regarding plastics and to raise awareness about the origins and risks of microplastics (Correa Rodriguez 2023).

Even the remote and highly prized marine protected area, Fernando de Noronha - an archipelago 360 km off the coast of Brazil, was noted by our reviewers as being threatened by both land-derived and ocean-derived sources of plastics. Our results complement those of a recent study which found that oceanographic characteristics and tourism infrastructure play an important role in the source, type and accumulation of marine debris. For example, ocean currents are known to transport marine debris to the windward, uninhabited coast of the archipelago, while locally generated debris affects the leeward coast (Grillo & Mello 2021). Indeed, authorities recognised the severity of this latter threat several years ago and published the first decree of its kind in Brazil in 2018 forbidding the entry, sale and use of single-use plastics (e.g. containers,

straws, disposable plastic cutlery and packaging and styrofoam) on the island (Marinho 2018; Grillo & Mello 2021).

However, reviewers identified multiple local and other anthropogenic threats to Fernando de Noronha such as: overcrowding of people in the site, perceived lack of investment in infrastructure, the site not seeming to contribute effectively to social equity in the local community, and the site being inadequately managed for tourism. Despite most of the environmental fees paid by tourists going towards the treatment and transportation of waste to the continent, increasing waste produced on the island is linked to an overpopulation of residents and visitors which is overloading local services (Marinho 2018).

5.5 Conclusions

Our evaluation of prevalent NCP expressed by visitors to Atlantic Ocean iconic marine sites demonstrates that the method of using Google Maps reviews can provide rapid, cost-efficient and relevant data on visitors' perceptions of different kinds of MPAs and marine tourism sites. Furthermore, the reviewers in our study identified unique combinations of socio-cultural (dis)benefits derived from the individual case study sites. Although the numbers of reviews available varied considerably across the sites, there was sufficient consistency among reviews to characterise individual sites based on the (dis)benefits and types of cultural practices conducted. We could therefore identify reviewers' collective preferences as well as specific points of interest and concern regarding marine tourism sites that could be used to inform management strategies for individual protected and non-protected sites and marine tourism in general.

Our novel approach of coding the socio-cultural (dis)benefits identified according to the 18 OHI Goals and Sub-Goals revealed the overall importance of five goals: Sense of Place, Tourism & Recreation, Livelihoods & Economies, Biodiversity, Clean Waters plus the additional code we created 'clean site'. The results highlight that reviewers highly value having the access and opportunity to visit aesthetically pleasing and well conserved marine environments for play and exercise, where they can practice various active and/or passive activities and interact with marine biodiversity.

The range of (dis)benefits identified by visitors to the case study sites highlight several contemporary and future ocean challenges that policy-makers, resource managers and tourism industry stakeholders ought to prioritise in site management strategies. Broadly speaking, these challenges include management and conservation of: ecosystems and species within sites to promote recovery of fish biomass and species diversity and improve socio-ecological resilience through increased adaptive capacity of local communities; the natural and cultural values that attract visitors and stimulate social and economic benefits for local residents; tourism within and around protected marine and coastal areas to avoid over-exploitation of local natural resources; and human activities in nearby areas that may cause detrimental effects to the natural resources and biodiversity that visitors wish to experience.

More specifically, critical strategies for achieving visitor satisfaction emerging from this study include: reduction and removal of marine litter from coastal areas; provision and upkeep of on-site facilities such as toilets to ensure health and safety of visitors and avoid polluting the natural environment; maintenance of access roads, clear signage and up to date information about accessibility to sites; management of visitor expectations through accurate advertising and provision of up to date information; delivery of tourism experiences that align with visitor values, budgets and the available natural resources; and communication

programs that convey how entrance fees (and other sources of income) are invested in site management, among other things.

Given the diverse geographic distribution of our sites and the commonality of the threats that reviewers reported, it is likely our findings reflect the existence of a broad pattern of threats to iconic marine sites around the Atlantic Ocean. The numerous and diverse wellbeing benefits received by site reviewers and our estimate of annual visitor revenue of nearly US\$207 million reveal the extent of public desire to visit iconic marine sites and a willingness to pay for cultural services provided by healthy sites. This also hints at the amount of public funds for site management, conservation and promotion that could be lost should all tourists avoid these sites due to the significant threats we identified. The financial and social wellbeing loss related to marine tourism and investment in local businesses and economies could be significantly higher.

6 Quantification of services to support economic and socio-cultural evaluations - Assessment of carbon sequestration services of the Atlantic Ocean

6.1 Background

The ocean plays a main role in regulating the climate; exchanging carbon dioxide (CO₂) with the atmosphere and absorbing, since the mid-1980s, about 20–30% of anthropogenic CO₂ (Bindoff et al., 2019). Annually the net removal is estimated to be 2–2.5 Pg of carbon from the atmosphere (Perruche et al., 2018, Iversen 2023) which accounts for 25% of the anthropogenic emissions for the same period, as estimated by Le Quéré et al., (2018) in 10.8 PgC/year. The estimates suggest that the ocean contains 38,000 PgC as inorganic carbon compared to the 900 PgC in the atmosphere (ca 40 times more; Ricour et al., 2023).

The oceanic carbon pump that sequesters the CO₂ is composed of two connected processes: a **physical carbon pump** and a **biological carbon pump**. The physical carbon pump refers to the transfer of carbon through physical processes like transport, mixing, and upwelling/downwelling, and is responsible for the net carbon uptake from the atmosphere. The **biological carbon pump** is based on carbon fixation by photosynthetic activity, and the transfer of carbon from the surface to the deepest parts of the ocean through gravitation, mixing, advection, and migration.

The biological carbon pump (BCP) plays a key role in the ocean for carbon sequestration through a set of processes: in the euphotic zone (<100 m) autotrophic organisms (i.e. phytoplankton) convert CO₂ into Particulate Organic Carbon (POC) or dissolved organic carbon (DOC, in form of excretions) via the **soft-tissue carbon** C_{soft} and particulate inorganic carbon (calcium carbonate) via the **hard-tissue pump** (Planchat et al., 2023). The organic carbon, together with ocean mixing and zooplankton migration, is then vertically transferred to the mesopelagic zone. In the mesopelagic regions (ca. 100-1000 m depth), the food web plays a central role in the export fluxes from the upper euphotic zone and the interior of the ocean. Remineralization of POC, DOC results in the biogenic production of Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC_{bio}) that unites with the one coming from the physical pump (Ricour et al., 2023). Most of the organic matter is remineralized in the upper ocean (producing DIC_{bio}), where it can quickly be returned to the atmosphere as CO₂. While the first part of the BCP, initialised by photosynthetic activity, occurs in the surface levels of the oceans, gravity makes the others occur along the water column (Ricour et al., 2023). Overall, BCP process transports carbon from the surface ocean to the interior sequestering it for months to millennia depending on the depth but also on the oceanographic conditions (Ricour et al., 2023). Table 1 provides a synthesis of the key processes involved in carbon storage and sequestration in the open ocean.

In this work we focus on the regulating service (CICES, 2021) of the ocean's carbon sequestration process, focusing on the BCP, which accounts for about 70% of the ocean's carbon sequestration capacity, in comparison to the hard-tissue pump (20%) (formed by hard structures of calcium carbonate skeletons of marine organisms) and the physical solubility pump (10%) (net carbon uptake from the atmosphere) (Sarmiento & Gruber 2006).

The understanding of the processes determining the remineralization of organic matter and its fate still presents uncertainties. For instance production of the DIC_{bio} depends also on the mesopelagic food web,

while the time for the return of DIC_{bio} to the ocean surface depends on the depth and on physical oceanographic features, with deeper penetration meaning a longer mean sequestration time (Figure 1 on the right). However, a small amount of DOC and POC is directly exported to the mesopelagic zone by the BCP to the long term C sequestration (Sarmiento and Gruber 2006). The timescale considered climatically significant for carbon sequestration is conventionally 100 years, but few studies have explicitly quantified the century scale flux of carbon sequestration due to the difficulties in assessing the residence time of the water masses (Ricour et al., 2023). Generally, it has been considered that the flux below 1000 m is stored for a time considered enough to define the C sequestration (Barange et al., 2017), but recent studies suggests that roughly half of the global DIC_{bio} inventory is remineralized above 1,000 m, necessitating a re-evaluation of carbon sequestration estimates across the entire water column.

According to Siegel et al. (2023), less than 3% of net primary production (NPP) is exported to 1000 m depth, and less than 1% of NPP eventually reaches the deep seafloor where it can be sequestered for millennia. Together with the remineralization process, the transfer efficiency of the POC at 1000 m depth is an indicator of the efficiency of the BCP: the faster the POC sinks, the higher the proportion of POC that reaches the deep sea. However, other studies have also demonstrated that C sequestration can occur at any depth in the water column, in the continuous vertical sequestration process (Ricour et al., 2023; Siegel et al., 2021). Studies have shown significant geographic variation in how much carbon is sequestered for over 100 years at various ocean depths. For example, in the northeast Pacific Ocean, 85% of CO_2 injected at 1,000 meters is sequestered for over 100 years, while only 10% is sequestered in the northwest Atlantic.

Theoretically, the attenuation of the carbon flux in the water columns is represented by a function describing the decrease in flux with depth, the best known function being the “Martin curve” (Martin et al., 1987). The Martin curve models, based on the sediment trap observation, compute a transfer efficiency (TE) of the POC flux to 1000 m of the 15% assuming that the remaining 85% is mineralized and transferred back to the surface in the first 1000 m. The drivers of the spatial pattern of transfer efficiency (TE) of the POC flux at 1000 m depth are still under investigation (de Melo Virissimo et al., 2024, Rufas et a., 2024), and key processes are currently thought to be related to particle size, plankton community diversity and temperature, with TE being higher in colder waters due to slower microbial degradation (Weber et al., 2016).

Table 1. The BCP and its glossary

KEY FACTS on BCP**How the Biological Carbon Pump Works:**

Photosynthesis: Phytoplankton assimilates CO₂ from the atmosphere during photosynthesis in the sunlit surface layer of the ocean (the euphotic zone). The portion of carbon fixed by phytoplankton that is not respired back into the environment is the Net Primary Production (NPP).

Carbon Export: When phytoplankton die they form particulate organic carbon (POC), which sinks from the euphotic zone to deeper layers of the ocean. Other materials like fecal pellets, dead marine organisms also contribute to this sinking carbon.

Remineralization: As POC sinks, a portion of it is decomposed by bacteria and other microorganisms, releasing CO₂ back into the water column. Some of the POC continues to sink to the deep ocean, where it is stored for long periods.

Sequestration: The carbon that reaches deep ocean layers, or sea bottom sediments, can be sequestered for centuries to millennia, effectively removing it from the atmosphere and helping to regulate the global climate.

Key Components of the BCP:

Gravitational Pump: The sinking of organic particles, primarily phytoplankton and zooplankton fecal pellets, is the primary mechanism for transporting carbon to the deep ocean.

Mixing and Advection: Physical processes like ocean mixing and currents also play a role in transporting dissolved and particulate organic carbon in the water column (both vertical and lateral transport).

Migrant Pump: Marine animals, such as zooplankton, that migrate vertically in the water column daily or seasonally contribute to carbon transport by consuming carbon-rich material at the surface and releasing it at depth.

Importance of the BCP:

Regulating CO₂ Levels and climate: By removing carbon from the surface ocean, where it can quickly return to the atmosphere, and storing it in the deep ocean, the biological pump helps maintain lower atmospheric CO₂ levels. This long-term carbon sequestration is critical for controlling the greenhouse effect and regulating Earth's climate.

Glossary

Carbon flux via the biological carbon pump: is the flux of carbon downward export through gravitational settling, ocean mixing, and migrations.

Carbon export / export production: the flux of carbon leaving the surface ocean and sinking into the ocean interior up to given depth horizon (100 m, 1000 m or the euphotic zone)

Remineralization: remineralization (respiration) of organic sinking carbon (POC) in the deeper ocean (formation of DIC_{bio}).

Attenuation of the POC flux with depth: average depth at which organic carbon is respired (or remineralised to DIC_{bio}).

Carbon residence time: time the carbon of biogenic origins takes to return to the surface ocean and atmosphere.

Carbon stock via the biological carbon pump: Fraction of carbon of biogenic origins (DOC, POC, DIC_{org}) remaining in the deep ocean.

Transfer efficiency: the proportion of particulate organic carbon (POC) that is successfully transferred from the surface ocean to deeper layers, relative to the total amount of downward organic carbon exported from the surface layers. It measures how effectively carbon that is exported from the surface reaches a specified depth, typically 1,000 or 2,000 meters. In Wilson et al., 2022 this term is referred to as the percentage of particulate organic carbon that is exported at 100 m and reaches 1,000 m

depth.

100-Year time horizon: Carbon sequestered for over 100 years is considered climatically significant, based on the 100-year time frame commonly used to evaluate durable carbon sequestration.

Cseq_{time}: total carbon produced in a certain location in the ocean and then remineralised, which remains in the ocean for a certain amount of time. In general, sequestered carbon is considered to affect the global climate when it stays in the ocean at least for 100 years. This is calculated by reconstructing the residence time of water from a circulation model. The residence time is a model-derived metric only, is not widely applicable to all models, and is not an observable quantity. However, it has the advantage of linking carbon storage to its source location before ocean transport.

Csoft: the respired carbon concentration in the ocean at a specific time. This physical quantity can be derived from both observations and ocean models (e.g., via AOU in Wilson et al., 2022). Csoft defines the carbon storage by its downstream location, i.e., after ocean transport, and cannot be traced back to its source location (to where the organic carbon has been produced).

Figure 1: The biological carbon pump (BCP) or soft-tissue pump Csoft. In the euphotic-zone food web, phytoplankton produces NPP and many following ecological and biogeochemical processes occur that transport organic carbon to the mesophotic zone through the mixing, gravitational and migrant pump (Figure 1 a). In this phase, a large part of the organic carbon (DOC, POC) is remineralized to DIC by bacterial activity and returns to the surface (within 1-100 years). Beneath this zone, in the mesophotic zone, organic carbon is remineralized back to DIC via food-web processes. The depths to which that organic carbon is transported set the timescale of its sequestration which can range from 100 to 1000 years. From the review of Siegel et al., 2024.

The BCP is composed of 3 different pumps (Figure 1B): the **gravitational** pump, the **migration** pump and the **mixing** pump. The gravitational pump quantifies the flux of organic carbon driven by the sinking of particles (aggregates, fecal pellets, phytoplankton cells) and represents the main contributor to the net carbon export being the only one that can deliver significant amounts of POC to the deep ocean where carbon can be sequestered for ≥ 100 years. The amount of organic carbon (POC) exported by sinking decreases with increasing depth as it is consumed by filter feeders and bacteria or solubilized to DOC and DIC_{biog} by microbes. At the same time, the sinking rate is altered by the aggregation and disaggregation of particles. The literature reports that generally POC exported below the mixed layer into the upper mesopelagic zone (200–500 m) can be stored for decades. In contrast, POC that reaches the lower mesopelagic zone (500–1,000 m) and beyond may be stored for centuries, depending on the location (Robinson et al., 2014).

The sequestration of organic carbon at the global level by the gravitational pump has an inventory budget of 1040 Pg C and turnover time of approximately 142 years (Siegel et al., 2023). The other 2 pumps that contribute to the injection of POC and DOC in the depth are the **mixing pump**, that quantifies the net transport by physical ocean circulation and mixing process and the **migrant pump** which considers the vertically migrating zooplankton and nekton on both daily and longer timescales. The mixing pump contributes to the total sequestration with 102 Pg C and a rapid turnover time (54 years). The migrant pump has a maximum export at 600 m and has a sequestration budget of 150 PgC and 150 years of sequestration time (Siegel et al., 2024).

The difference between the relatively fast timescale of sinking particles (days/weeks) versus the much longer timescales of ocean circulation (10 to 1000 years), leads to the accumulation of dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC_{biog}) in the ocean effectively lowering the baseline atmospheric CO_2 concentration by ~ 150 to 250 ppm (Wilson et al., 2022 and reference therein).

The amount of carbon sequestered by the BCP, are a function of 1) the export production, i.e., the amount of carbon that flux in the deeper ocean, 2) the attenuation of the POC flux with depth based on the depth at which the POC are respired back to DIC_{biog} and 3) the DIC_{biog} sequestration time. The scheme in Figure 1 synthesizes the main processes that are at the base of the carbon sequestration services based on the BCP in the ocean.

Calculating ocean carbon sequestration is challenging due to the complexity and variability of the ocean's processes and to the efforts needed to capture them from the observational analytical and modelling perspectives. The BCP processes vary across regions, depths, and seasons, making accurate modeling difficult. Carbon storage efficiency also varies by location, with deep oceans generally storing carbon more effectively than shallow waters, but this is also influenced by circulation and by thermal patterns. Each key process (primary production, advection and mixing, remineralization and migration) act at different timescales, adding further complexity. Limited data exacerbates these difficulties. While satellites provide good surface-level insights, in-situ measurements of deeper processes are sparse, making it hard to track carbon flux. Additionally, much of the carbon exported is remineralized before it reaches ocean depth, and the rate of this process varies regionally. Models estimating carbon sequestration rely on assumptions that don't fully capture ocean complexity, and these factors together make accurate real-time carbon sequestration calculations difficult. Computing ocean carbon storage involves tracking a wide array of biological and physical processes

requiring the integration of several observational analytical and modelling methods and tools, such as remote sensing, in-situ observations, chemical analysis, and advanced numerical models, as summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Processes and methods used to assess the different components of the BCP

PROCESSES AND METHODS TO ASSESS BCP
<p>1. Photosynthesis and Primary Production:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Satellite Remote Sensing: Satellites measure ocean color to estimate chlorophyll concentration and net primary production (NPP), which indicates phytoplankton activity and CO₂ uptake.● In-situ Measurements: Measures of light penetration, and nutrient availability, to assess productivity.
<p>2. Particulate Organic Carbon (POC) Export:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Sediment Traps: collecting sinking particles at various depths to directly measure POC flux.● Optical Sensors: Underwater instruments like transmissometers or backscattering sensors measure particle concentrations as they sink, giving indirect estimates of POC flux.● Satellite-derived Models: Satellite NPP data is used in models to estimate POC export based on empirical relationships between surface productivity and export flux.
<p>3. Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC) and POC Transport via physical processes such as mixing, upwelling, and downwelling:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Oceanographic Surveys: Ships and autonomous devices (like Argo floats) measure DIC concentrations at different depths.● Chemical Tracers: Ocean circulation models● In-situ Sensors: of pCO₂, alkalinity, and DIC● Ocean Circulation Models: Models such as the Ocean Circulation Inverse Model (OCIM) and general circulation models (GCMs) simulate how carbon and other tracers move through the ocean.● Tracer Studies: Tracers like chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), radiocarbon (C14), and noble gases help to estimate the rates of deep ocean water formation and mixing.
<p>4. Remineralization of POC into (DIC_{bio}) CO₂ :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Sediment Traps: The change in POC flux with depth is used to infer remineralization rates.● Dissolved Oxygen Profiles: Since oxygen is consumed during remineralization, oxygen concentration profiles can indirectly indicate remineralization intensity.● Biogeochemical Models: Models simulate the production and decay of organic carbon and estimate remineralization rates, using data on nutrients and oxygen consumption.
<p>5. Zooplankton and Migrant Pump:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCPs): These devices detect the vertical movement of zooplankton and fish, allowing for the estimation of carbon transport via the migrant pump.○ Zooplankton Sampling: Nets and other sampling tools measure zooplankton biomass and fecal pellet production, contributing to carbon export estimates.
<p>6. Sedimentation and Long-Term Storage:</p>

- **Sediment Cores:** Sediment cores are extracted to measure the accumulation of carbon over time, providing a record of long-term sequestration.
- **Isotope Analysis:** Isotope ratios (e.g., carbon isotopes) in sediment layers help determine the origin and age of the carbon stored in ocean sediments.

7. Carbon Sequestration Efficiency (Transfer Efficiency):

- **Modeling Approaches:** Transfer efficiency can be estimated using biogeochemical models that simulate carbon export and its attenuation with depth.
- **Sediment Traps:** Changes in POC flux at different depths are used to calculate how much carbon escapes remineralization and reaches the deep ocean.

In this study, we estimated the carbon storage for the Atlantic Ocean by applying two methods: a method based on model assessments of POC fluxes and of mineralization of POC (Wilson et al., 2022) and a method that integrates the contribution of gravitational, migrant and mixing pumps (Nowicki et al., 2022), using models and observations. Following Wilson et al., (2022) we assess the carbon flux of POC at 1000 m depth and the inventory of sequestered carbon, i.e. how much carbon the Atlantic Ocean stores through the BCP (Csoft), using data from three Earth system models at the present time. The Csoft represents the Atlantic mean BCP carbon storage (PgC) and was calculated from the difference between modeled oxygen concentrations and the theoretical concentrations of saturated O₂ (Apparent Oxygen Utilisation (AOU) converted to carbon units using a stoichiometric ratio of carbon to oxygen. In addition, we compared the Csoft results with estimates from another work (Nowicki et al., 2022) that uses a model that integrates satellite and oceanographic data with an ecosystem-biogeochemistry-circulation model to quantify carbon export and sequestration through the ocean's biological carbon pump. The model simulates an upper-ocean food web, including small and large phytoplankton, small and large zooplankton, and vertically migrating zooplankton. In the Nowicki et al., (2022) methods, the total carbon export is assessed as the sum of gravitational (POC respiration), migrant (zooplankton respiration) and mixing (DOC respiration) pumps.

In this work, **the economic valuation of the ecosystem service** has been calculated using the BGC carbon storage inventory (Csoft) for the Atlantic Ocean rather than the fluxes. Previous studies based on coupled ocean dynamic and biogeochemical models, have focused either on the total fluxes of carbon sequestered in the ocean, calculated at the sea surface, including biological, physical and carbonate pumps at the scale of the Mediterranean Sea (Canu et al., 2015), or on carbon fluxes quantified such as the carbon export (POC export) beyond 500 and 1000 m depth (Barange et al., 2017).

To evaluate **economically** the benefits of the Atlantic ecosystems in relation to their carbon storage services we use the concept of Social Cost of Carbon (SCC). The SCC is a key tool in climate change policy, used in the design and evaluation of mitigation policies, such as energy efficiency standards or emission cuts (see e.g.: Pearce 2003, Griffiths et al., 2012; Nordhaus, 2014, 2017; Rennert et al., 2022, EPA 2022). The SCC measures the damage cost of emitting an additional unit of carbon dioxide or other equivalent greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. It is composed of the sum of all future discounted damages originated by emitting (usually) one ton of carbon or CO₂. In economic terms, it is the change in the discounted value of money-metric economic welfare that results from a unit increase in emissions. Using economic jargon, it represents the “marginal” cost to society.

The SCC is usually calculated using simulation models that link carbon emissions with changes in social welfare, known as integrated assessment models (IAMs) (Dietz, 2012).

6.2 Methods

The input data are from the historical simulations of 3 Earth system models (ESM) belonging to the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6; Eyring et al., 2016): GFDL-ESM4 (Dunne et al., 2020), IPSL-CM6A-LR (Boucher et al., 2020), MPI-ESM1-2-HR (Mauritsen et al., 2019). The carbon biological pump of the pelagic ecosystem is resolved in all the models at the lower trophic levels (plankton groups), as detailed in Table 3.

Table 3: Overview of the ocean and marine biogeochemical components of 3 ESM CMIP6 (Seferian et al. 2020, Wilson et al., 2022)

Models	Ocean Model	Biogeochemical model	Marine Resolution (lat × lon)	Planktonic group	Sinking velocity of POC:	Remineralisation of POC
GFDL-ESM4	GFDL-O M4p5	COBALTv2 (Stock et al.,)	0.5° × 0.5° (50 km)	PHYTO: 3 explicit (small, large, diaz), 1 implicit (diatoms) ZOOPL: 3 (micro + 2 meso)	Fixed	Function of T, dissolved [O ₂] and ballasting by minerals (ballasting is implemented as a fixed length-scale reflecting either faster sinking or slower remineralisation due to protection).
IPSL-CM6A-LR	NEMO-O PA	PISCESv2 (Aumont et al., 2015)	0.3°-1° (100km)	PHYTO:2 (diatoms, nanophyto) ZOOPL: 2 (microzoo, mesozoo)	Small particles have a fixed sinking velocity, large particles have increasing velocity with depth. Production of small and large particles is a fixed function of calcification and silification, i.e., a form of ballasting.	Function of T, dissolved [O ₂], aggregation dynamics.
MPI-ESM1-2-HR	MPIOM1 .63	HAMOCC6 (Paulsen et al., 2017)	1.5° X1.5° (150km)	PHYTO: 2 (bulk, cyano) ZOOPL: 1	Fixed	Reduces at low dissolved oxygen concentration.

COBALTv2 (in GFDL-ESM 4), displays the highest trophic complexity level with 3 explicit phytoplankton classes, 1 implicit phytoplankton class, 3 explicit zooplankton classes and 1 explicit heterotrophic bacteria class; PISCESv2 (in IPSL-CM6A-LR) includes 4 explicit plankton types (2 phytoplankton and 2 zooplankton), while HAMOCC6 (in MPI-ESM1-2-HR) include 2 phytoplankton and 1 zooplankton types (Seferian et al., 2020).

All data of the historical simulation (1850 - 2014) are detrended for the internal drift derived from errors of the model calculating as the difference between the equivalent part of the control experiment (piControl) starting from the branch point (1850-1869):

$$C_{\text{softDETRENDED}} = C_{\text{Soft HISTORICAL}}(1995-2014) - (\text{drift}[C_{\text{Soft CNTR}}(1995-2014)] - \text{baseline}[C_{\text{Soft CNTR}}(1850-1869)])$$

The **POC flux** at 1000, the **transfer efficiency** (POC flux at 1000/ POC flux at 100*100) and the carbon sequestered at 1000m - **Csoft**- are calculated with the monthly averages from 1995 to 2014 from the historical simulation (1850-2014). Three-dimensional fields for POC fluxes were extracted at 1,000 m and annually averaged before calculating export production.

The POC flux at 1000 m is considered a good proxy for the Csoft at or near equilibrium, i.e., an ocean under minimal perturbation representing a reliable predictor of the impact that POC will have on Csoft.

The BCP carbon storage (Pg C) Csoft is then calculated as follows (Eq. 1):

$$C_{\text{soft}} = \frac{1}{V_{\text{tot}}} \int_V [AOU] R_{C:O} m_C dv \quad (1)$$

where AOU is the three-dimensional fields of apparent oxygen utilization calculated as:

$AOU = O_2 - O_{2,sat}$, and where, $R_{C:O}$ is the stoichiometric ratio between carbon and oxygen (117:170), m_C is the molecular weight of carbon (12.01 g mol^{-1}), V_{tot} is the total ocean volume. For details on the methodology see Wilson et al., 2021.

The second approach follows that of Nowicki et al., (2022), in which the authors use an ensemble of numerical models of the biological pump that simulates an upper ocean food web model assimilating satellite and in situ observations of oceanic biogeochemistry to adjust the POC and DOC produced in the euphotic zone that contributes to C sequestration. In this work, based on the estimate of Nowicki et al., 2022, we evaluate the total carbon export as the sum of gravitational (POC respiration), migrant (zooplankton respiration) and mixing (DOC respiration) pumps. The difference between the two approaches is that the CMIP6 model simulations analyzed by Wilson et al., (2022) are transient ocean models with a climate forcing changing over time. In contrast, Nowicki et al., (2022) have a static modern climate (it does not change with time) and a biological pump model that is calibrated to reproduce direct observational constraints such as nutrient distributions, as accurately as possible.

The respiration of organic carbon in the ocean interior leads to carbon storage as dissolved inorganic carbon. This carbon storage can be quantified in two ways:

(1) **Csoft** - the spatial distribution of respired carbon concentration in the ocean **after the respired carbon has been transported by ocean circulation**. This has the advantage of being a physical quantity that can be derived from both observations and ocean models (e.g., via AOU in Wilson et al., 2022). However, Csoft

defines storage by its downstream location, i.e., after ocean transport, and cannot be traced back to its source location.

(2) **Cseq** - the total carbon storage that has originated from a given location. This is calculated by reconstructing the residence time of water from a circulation model or using lagrangian approaches. This is a model-derived metric only, is not widely applicable to all models, and is not an observable quantity. However, it has the advantage of linking carbon storage to its source location before ocean transport. In short, Csoft and Cseq quantify the same carbon storage but are defined by a downstream or upstream (source) location. Csoft is observable and widely applicable whilst Cseq provides the explicit assessment of carbon storage from its source location but in more limited applications.

Economic assessment

To assess the economic value of carbon sequestration we take the SCC reference value(s) from Tol (2023). This is a meta-analysis of estimates on the SCC from 207 papers published before 2022. Then we use the average values of the estimates to “price” the tons of CO₂ sequestered by the Atlantic Ocean ecosystems. Table 4 reports the estimated values both from the empirical and Kernel estimation processes developed and applied by the author.

Table 4. Empirical and kernel average standard deviation of estimates of the Social Cost of Carbon (US\$ per ton of C) by pure rate of time preference. Source: Adapted from Tol (2023)

Pure rate of time preference (%)*	Empirical	Kernel
3	43	72
2	238	714
1	155	342
0	407	342
All studies	179	458

The pure rate of time preference (PRTP) is that component of the social discount rate that accounts for uncertainty aversion in individual preferences. A 3% PRTP means that the future “depreciates” at a rate of 3% per year (e.g. one dollar received next year is worth less than one dollar received today. It is worth exactly 0.97 dollars today). 0% PRTP means that the future is as important as the present or that there is no depreciation.

6.3 Results

Transfer efficiency at 1000 m:

The average TE at 1000 m of the three models at present condition (1995-2014) is 17% ± 9. The spatial distribution of TE varies among the models, with GFDL-ESM4 and MPI-ESM1-2-HR showing great transfer efficiency mainly in the upwelling areas, while IPSL-CM6A-LR shows high transfer in areas of high surface productivity (Figure 2). Indeed, the results showed a stronger transfer efficiency in the middle (GFDL-ESM4 and MPI-ESM1-2-HR) and high latitudes of the NA (IPSL-CM6A-LR; max 61%) (Figure 3). In general, the TE is higher in the IPSL model (mean 25%), which is the only one of the three models investigated to show a constant sink rate over time, although this increases with depth (Aumont et al., 2015; Table 1), while TE is lower in the GFDL (14%) and in the MPI (11%).

Figure 2: Spatial distribution of the transfer efficiency of POC at 1000 m expressed as a percentage. From left to right are shown the maps for GFDL, IPSL, MPI ESM belonging to the CMIP6.

Figure 3: Transfer efficiency at 1000 in percentage as extracted from the 3 ESM model (GFDL, IPSL, MPI).

Particulate organic carbon flux at 1000 meter: All three models show the highest flux export at 1000 m in the eastern boundary upwelling regions (EBUS), the Gulf Stream, and its extension into the North Atlantic Current. Notably, the upwelling along the northwest coast of Africa, which drives a localized region of high productivity, exhibits the highest level of export, reaching a maximum of $27.89 \text{ gC m}^2\text{y}^{-1}$ in the IPSL model. Another important area for carbon sequestration is the Southern Ocean, especially in accordance with the IPSL model (Figure 4).

The total amount of POC that reaches 1000 m in the Atlantic Ocean is higher in the IPSL model (0.47 PgCy^{-1}) followed by GFDL (0.23 PgCy^{-1}) and MPI (0.18 PgCy^{-1}) (Table 5).

Table 5: Summary of the total Atlantic POC flux at 1000 m depth in petagrams of carbon for the three ES models. The mean values of gC for m^2 and their standard deviation are also given.

POC flux at 1000 m ESM – present	Sum PgC y^{-1}	Mean $\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{y}^{-1}$	sd
GFDL-ESM4_historical_1995_2014_expc	0.23	2.62	1.43
IPSL-CM6A-LR_historical_1995_2014_expc	0.47	5.20	3.64
MPI-ESM1-2-HR_historical_1995_2014_expc	0.18	1.80	1.82

Figure 4: The POC flux at 1000 m as $\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{y}^{-1}$ for the three models investigated. (A) represents the spatial distribution, while (B) represents the data value (x-axis) versus the latitudinal distribution (y-axis)

Carbon stock:

The Csoft, represents the total carbon stored in the Atlantic and it is represented as an average among the 3 models is 310.72 Pg C \pm 0.84 sd (Figure 5, Table 6). The results show that the Atlantic Ocean acts as a weak sink of atmospheric carbon representing 17% of the global carbon sequestration (ca 1758 PgC).

gCsoft - models ensemble

Figure 5: Mean and Sd of Csoft as TgC, calculated from the 3 ESM. Figure A shows the Csoft in TgC as the mean of the three Earth system models (GFDL, IPSL, MPI); Figure B shows the standard deviation.

The Csoft represents the spatial distribution of respired carbon concentration in the ocean **after the carbon has been transported (where it is respired) by ocean circulation**: Csoft defines carbon storage by its downstream location, i.e., after ocean transport, and cannot be traced back to its source location.

Figure 6: Latitudinal gradients of Csoft distribution averaged over the 3 ESM.

Figure 7: Csoft as TgC as detailed for the 3 models.

Table 6: Total Csoft for the Atlantic basin at the present conditions for the 3 ESM

Model	Temporal resolution	Global estimates of Csoft PgC	tot_PgC in the Atlantic	% of the global estimates
<i>GFDL</i>	<i>1995-2014</i>	<i>1705.554</i>	<i>299.35</i>	<i>14.55</i>
<i>IPSL-CM6A-LR</i>	<i>1995-2014</i>	<i>1891.150</i>	<i>373.44</i>	<i>19.75</i>
<i>MPI-ESM1-2-HR</i>	<i>1995-2014</i>	<i>1677.622</i>	<i>259.38</i>	<i>15.46</i>
Nowicki methods	Temporal resolution		tot_PgC in the Atlantic	
Csoft-respiration	Total	Steady-state	–	194.54
Cseq-respiration	Total	Steady-state	–	346.19

The results of the Cseq calculated from the Nowicki model represent all the 3 components of the BCP, and their optimized version of the model, the processes reflect a combination of food-web and temperature effects. This translates into higher export ratio in regions dominated by large populations, due to the shorter food-web, more efficient aggregation formation and exports. As shown in Figure 8, carbon storage is analyzed with 2 different approaches (from Nowicki et al., 2022). On the right side, the carbon storage inventory (Cseq) of the respired carbon stored by the ocean at steady state is shown, assuming an instantaneous equilibrium of the respired CO₂ with the atmosphere. Note that this calculation shows the spatial pattern of the POC flux at depth, with a higher concentration of TgC in the upwelling regions and in the North Atlantic (Gulf Stream region); on the left, the Csoft quantification based on total remineralization in the water column is shown. In this case, the analysis is based on observational data from the work of Nowicki et al., (2022). As shown, the pattern is coherent with that calculated by the AOU from the CMIP6 models (Figures 6 and 7) and is mainly determined by the remineralization rate and bathymetry.

As illustrated in Figure 8, carbon storage is analyzed using two distinct approaches based on the methodologies of Wilson et al., (2022) and Nowicki et al., (2022).

On the right side of Figure 8, the carbon storage inventory (Cseq) depicts the respired carbon stored in the ocean at steady state, under the assumption of an instantaneous equilibrium between the respired CO₂ and the atmosphere (Wilson et al., 2022). This calculation reveals the spatial distribution of POC flux at depth, with a noticeable concentration of carbon (TgC) in upwelling regions and the North Atlantic, particularly the Gulf Stream area.

On the left side of Figure 8, the quantification of Csoft, which is based on total remineralization throughout the water column, is presented. This analysis utilizes observational data from Nowicki et al. (2022), and the resulting pattern aligns well with the estimates calculated using AOU from CMIP6 models (as shown in Figures 6 and 7). The spatial distribution of carbon storage in this case is primarily influenced by remineralization rates and the underlying bathymetry of the ocean.

Figure 8: Carbon storage is analyzed with 2 different approaches (from Nowicki et al., 2022). On the left side, the carbon storage inventory (Cseq) and on the right, the Csoft quantification based on total remineralization in the water column.

Economic assessment:

Table 7 reports the outcome of the procedure consisting in using the figures of Table 4 to evaluate the carbon sequestration estimates reported in Table 6 once converted to tons of C.

By pooling all the studies, the average value of the service ranges from \$ 46.6 trillion using MPI-ESM1-2-HR model estimates and the empirical method to the US\$171 trillion using the IPSL-CM6A-LR model estimates and the Kernel method.

The highest values reported from the empirical estimates are the \$ 152 trillion corresponding to a PRTP of 0% and associated with the IPSL-CM6A-LR model. The highest value reported by Kernel estimates is the \$ 266 trillion associated with a 2% PRTP and, again, the IPSL-CM6A-LR model.

Table 7. Economic value of the carbon sequestration service from Atlantic ecosystems (\$US Trillion) using empirical and kernel average standard deviation of estimates of the Social Cost of Carbon by pure rate of time preference and by models

	Empirical			Kernel		
	MPI-ESM1-2-H R	GFDL	IPSL-CM6A- LR	MPI-ESM1-2-H R	GFDL	IPSL-CM6A-LR
3	11,2	12,9	16,1	18,7	21,6	26,9
2	61,7	71,2	88,9	185,2	213,7	266,6
1	40,2	46,4	57,9	88,7	102,4	127,7
0	105,6	121,8	152,0	88,7	102,4	127,7
All	46,4	53,6	66,8	118,8	137,1	171,0

6.4 Discussion

Carbon sequestration by the ocean is still difficult to assess due to high uncertainty in knowledge regarding deep ocean functioning, and residence times which have a major role in carbon sequestration.

The traditional modelling approaches to quantify and economically assess carbon sequestration in the ocean relies predominantly on measuring the flux of carbon at the surface as a proxy (Canu et al., 2015), or on using the fluxes calculated at a fixed depth, usually set at 1000 m, as a benchmark (from an economic perspective: Barange et al., 2017) to calculate only the fraction assumed to be stored over longer periods of time. This last method has gained acceptance mainly because it provides a measure of how much carbon is transported from the surface to the deep sea (>1000 m), where it is assumed to be effectively removed from the atmosphere over long periods of time (>100 years).

However, recent studies question this fixed-depth approach and indicate that carbon sequestration can also occur at shallower depths and still contribute significantly to long-term carbon storage. Ricour et al., (2024) argue that remineralization of organic carbon above 1000 m, particularly due to the specific geographic location of sinking particles, can result in carbon being sequestered for more than 100 years. This finding means that the traditional fixed-depth approach may underestimate the true extent of carbon sequestration in the ocean, but provides a conservative estimate.

Our study addresses this potential underrepresentation by incorporating both conventional fixed-depth fluxes and a comprehensive carbon inventory across the entire water column (Wilson et al., 2022). This dual approach allows us to compare our results with the established literature while exploring new dimensions of carbon sequestration and facilitating comparison between different studies (Table 8). At the same time, the broader inventory method adopted provides a more comprehensive understanding of how carbon is distributed and stored in the water column.

Transfer efficiency (TE) of the particulate organic carbon (POC) flux, expressed as the ratio between the POC@1000/POC@100, refers to the fraction of POC that sinks from the surface ocean and reaches deeper layers, such as 1000 m. The transfer efficiency (TE) of the POC and the POC export at 1000 m are controlled mainly by the particle size, the diversity of the plankton communities and the temperature. Temperature-dependent remineralization included in the EMS2 model (GFDL and IPSL) affects the depth at

which most of this decomposition occurs leading to an enhanced transfer efficiency in cold, high-latitude waters where a slower microbial degradation occurs.

The Atlantic Ocean exhibits different patterns of **carbon flux** into the deep sea that vary with the latitudinal gradient. In spite of some differences and variability among models, the spatial pattern is consistent in the **POC flux at 1000** (Figure 4A) and is consistent with other studies based on biogeochemical assimilated models (Nowicki et al., 2022). Low carbon export is particularly evident in the subtropical gyres, which are characterized by low productivity due to the stratified water column, which reduces the supply of nutrients to the sea surface, and by warm water, which increases the metabolic rates of organic remineralization at shallower depths. Stratified water masses contribute to reducing the supply of nutrients to the surface ocean, limiting productivity, but also the supply of respired DIC leading to the accumulation of respired CO₂ in the ocean interior (Wilson et al., 2022). In contrast, the tropical and upwelling areas are characterized by higher productivity due to large-scale equatorial and coastal upwelling of nutrients and a colder and less oxygenated water column that reduces POC decomposition.

The North Atlantic, as shown in Figure 4A, is another region with high carbon exports due to high productivity, cold water temperature and deep winter mixed layers. In addition, this area is characterized by deep water formation in the Labrador Sea and the Nordic Seas, which increases the rate of carbon transport in the deep ocean. The Southern Ocean is the zone where the models are more uncertain. However, the high carbon export in the sub-Antarctic region at about 40°S (Figure 4A) is still evident due to the highly productive spring bloom. In contrast, the adjacent regions are characterized by low productivity and strong upwelling, which brings inorganic carbon back to the sea surface (Nowicki et al., 2022).

The subpolar regions are characterized by highly productive spring blooms. Moreover, the Subpolar North Atlantic is a deep water formation region at the start of the deep ocean conveyor. In the table below are reported the values estimated by the literature and by the present work both for the carbon flux and the carbon storage (Table 8). The results show that the methodology applied to the ESM tends to overestimate the sequestration stock compared to the literature results.

Table 8: A synthesis of the C sequestration flux and inventories based on the literature.

Reference	Global flux export at 1000m (PgC m ⁻² y ⁻¹) - gravitational pump	Carbon stock (PgC)- BGC total	Methods
Nowicki et al. 2022	10.2	1293	Food-web model +bgc model
Carter et al., 2021	–	1300	O ₂ budget and circulation
This study (Wilson)		1758	CMIP6 POC flux a 1000m; CMIP6 AOU
Ricour et al., 2024	0.66 (0.9-2.6?)	–	Average of 7 configurations of CONVERSE model
Boyd et al., 2019		1000-3000	
Siegel et al., 2024		1040	

By shifting the focus from fluxes to inventory stock, this assessment provides a more comprehensive understanding of the processes themselves and their long-term contribution to ocean carbon sequestration.

The **carbon sequestration (Cseq)** calculations derived from the Nowicki model encompass all three components of the biological carbon pump (DOC, POC and zooplankton migration). The optimized version of this model effectively integrates both food-web dynamics and temperature, resulting in a comprehensive representation of the processes involved. This integration manifests as a higher export ratio in regions with large populations, attributable to shorter food webs, more efficient aggregation formation, and enhanced carbon export (Nowicki et al., 2022).

In addition, by comparing our results with the methods proposed by Nowicki et al., (2022), we deepen the concept of carbon sequestration inventory. This comparison allows us to refine our understanding of the mechanisms of carbon sequestration and to evaluate the methods currently available to quantify this important ecosystem service. The evaluations of damages from GHG emissions (which is the “dual” of the benefits from sequestering those emissions) is challenging, complex and uncertainty prone. Compounding all these complexities into one figure is highly debated and debatable with criticisms that have been addressed both to the models and methods used for climate change impact assessment and in particular IAMs (Stern, 2016; Pindyk 2017; Ganìmbir et al., 2019), and to the methods applied to derive and the concept itself of SCC (Pezzey 2018).

While acknowledging that, the discussion of strengths and weaknesses of SCC goes beyond the purposes of this section. We note however that it is an important reference value in the literature whose “evolution” driven by new knowledge and scientific evidence is constantly monitored by practitioners and policy makers (EPA 2022; Van der Vrist et al., 2023; Tol 2023).

Here we just mention three factors that are particularly relevant in determining the social cost of carbon.

The first is how damages are aggregated intra-temporally across different individuals, groups or communities. Given that damages from emissions affect heterogeneous “subjects”, the way in which this heterogeneity is considered, or the way in which distributional concerns are introduced, can affect the aggregated cost estimate.

The second is when the unit emission occurs. The later, the worse. This is due to the assumption that, with time passing, physical and economic systems are placed under increasing pressure from higher levels of climate change. Accordingly, one additional unit of emission becomes progressively more damaging as it is affecting a system which is more damaged already (Griffiths et al., 2012).

The third key factor determining the SCC is the choice of the discount rate. In short, the discount rate places a weight on different time periods (a more extensive discussion can be found in Pearce (1999)). This weight can be determined either “positively”, by observing, for instance, how markets reward intertemporal investments, or “normatively”, by assigning a subjective evaluation to the present against the future times.

One ton of CO₂ emitted today originates damages for hundreds of years given the long permanence of CO₂ in the atmosphere. A lower discount rate corresponds to a lower “depreciation of the future against the present”. Therefore, future damages remain important, and the discounted intertemporal summation will result in a higher SCC. The opposite applies to high discount rates.

7 Coastal Atlantic blue carbon ecosystem: Assessment of sequestration services from accumulation rates and stocks

7.1 Background

Coastal wetland ecosystems are known as "**blue carbon**" ecosystems (BCE), a term first introduced in the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) 2009 report "Blue Carbon" (Nellemann et al., 2009). The term was used to emphasise the significance of carbon sequestration and storage in highly productive coastal ecosystems, particularly as a policy measure for climate change mitigation. BCEs include habitats such as salt marshes, tidal flats, seagrass meadows, and mangroves, which play a relevant role in the global sequestration of carbon (C) (Macreadie et al., 2021). The BC ecosystems are capable of storing carbon in various pools, including living biomass both above-ground (leaves, stems, branches) and below-ground (roots), as well as in non-living biomass (e.g., litter and dead wood) (Macreadie et al., 2021). In particular, they sequester both allochthonous and autochthonous carbon in their sediments acting as long-term atmospheric carbon sinks, with sediment carbon potentially being preserved for extended periods because of their anoxic sediment environment (Chen and Lee, 2022b). The carbon sequestration concept has gained significant importance in climate change mitigation strategies, emphasising the value of these ecosystems and the potential benefits of their restoration as a nature-based solution (UNEA, 2022) to achieve carbon removal from the atmosphere through ecosystem management and reforestation (Macreadie et al., 2021).

In addition to the climate regulating services (Haines-Young 2018), the BCE generates a range of other ecosystem services such as nutrient and pollutant removal, promoting biodiversity, acting as nursery areas for many marine species, providing food for sustainable livelihoods and protecting coastal zones from storm surges and erosion (Macreadie et al., 2021).

To create a clear glossary of terms related to carbon sequestration, we provide the following definitions based on the literature:

Carbon sequestration is the process by which carbon is removed from the atmosphere and stored in the carbon pools of specific habitats, such as above-ground biomass (leaves, stems, branches), below-ground biomass (roots), and soil. More generally, the IPCC defines carbon sequestration as the process of increasing the C content of a C pool other than the atmosphere (IPCC, 2001).

Carbon stock (or carbon storage) is the absolute amount of carbon contained in a given pool (living or non-living) at a given time. It is expressed in grams of carbon per unit of habitat area. More generally, the carbon stock is the C content of each pool. The carbon stock is expressed as a mass.

The **carbon accumulation rate** is the rate at which carbon accumulates in pools that have a long turnover time. In the case of coastal ecosystems, it refers to the first metre of sediment (usually) where poor remineralization occurs. In the literature, it is often expressed as carbon accumulation rate (CAR) per unit area.

Figure 1. Conceptual model of the BCE and the representation of the carbon accumulation rate and carbon storage functions.

In this work, when we refer to carbon stock we consider in particular the below-ground carbon pools that represent the largest pool of C in vegetated coastal ecosystems and are composed of dead leaves, sediments, and roots (Howard et al., 2014) (Figure 1).

In particular, the below-ground carbon pools constitute 50% to over 90% of the total ecosystem carbon stock of mangroves, and more than 98% for tidal salt marshes and seagrasses (Fourqurean et al., 2014 and reference therein).

The Carbon Accumulation Rate CAR is calculated as the product of the sediment accretion rate (SAR) and average carbon density of the soil. SAR estimates may involve a variety of tracers and profiles of tracers, including long-term profiles of ^{137}Cs , ^{210}Pb and short-term marker horizons (Ouyang & Lee, 2014 and references therein). Chen and Lee (2022a) calculated CAR as follows (Eq. 2):

$$\text{CAR} = \text{SAR} * \text{CS}_{100\text{cm}} / 100\text{cm} \quad (2)$$

where SAR is the sediment accumulation rate (cm yr^{-1}) and $\text{CS}_{100\text{cm}}$ is the sediment C stock at the top metre of the tidal flats or mangroves ($\text{MgC}_{\text{org}} \text{ ha}^{-1}$).

The **soil carbon pool**, or carbon stock, is quantified using a globally accepted protocol (Howard et al., 2014), which involves analyzing soil cores subsampled to a specific depth, typically 1 m. This method takes into account the **dry bulk density** and **soil organic carbon content ($\%C_{\text{org}}$)**. Carbon density is calculated using these two parameters; however, because dry bulk density and $\%C_{\text{org}}$ can vary with depth and location, carbon density does not always follow a consistent pattern with depth.

According to Chen and Lee (2022b) the sediment carbon stock (CS) has been calculated as a standardised carbon stock at the 1 m of soil depth (Mg C ha^{-1}) as follows (Eq. 3-4):

$$CS_{1m} = BD * SC * 1m \quad (3)$$

or

$$CS_{1m} = CD * 1m \quad (4)$$

where BD is mean sediment bulk density (g cm^{-3} or kg m^{-3}), SC C content (%) and CD Carbon density (g C cm^{-3} or kg C m^{-3}), depending on the original studies from where the data are from (Chen and Lee, 2022b).

Seagrass is one of the world's most productive habitats forming extensive meadows in the coastal waters. This habitat type is composed of approximately 60 different species of underwater flowering plants, and it has a near-global distribution encompassing tropical and temperate latitudes. The seagrass leaves degrade slowly and, through their roots and rhizomes, seagrasses deposit large amounts of underground, partly mineralized, carbon. Thus, they constitute an important CO_2 sink, responsible for about 15% of the total carbon storage in the ocean (Kennedy et al., 2009).

Mangroves are trees, shrubs, palms or ground ferns which normally grow above mean sea level in the intertidal zone of marine, coastal, or estuarine environments. On a global scale, mangrove plants are a dominant ecosystem of many tropical and subtropical coastline regions of the world, and two species of *Avicennia* have penetrated the warm temperate areas of both hemispheres. The global distribution of mangroves generally matches the winter 20°C isotherm. Blue carbon storage in mangroves is disproportionate to their small area (ca 0.1% of the continental surface), $693 \text{ Mg C}_{\text{ORG}} \text{ ha}^{-1}$, with most of this carbon (74%) stored in deep soil horizons. Global stock estimates for mangroves are $5.23\text{--}8.63 \text{ Pg C}_{\text{ORG}}$ which is 15–24% of the total C stock in the tropical coastal ocean. Carbon burial accumulation rate in mangrove soils averages $184 \text{ g C}_{\text{ORG}} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ with global estimates ($9.6\text{--}15.8 \text{ Tg C}_{\text{ORG}} \text{ y}^{-1}$) reflecting their importance in carbon sequestration (Alongi, 2022).

Salt marshes are intertidal ecosystems vegetated by a variety of primary producers such as macroalgae, diatoms, and cyanobacteria, but physically dominated by vascular plants. In this habitat, the survival of the dominant vascular plants depends upon exposure to the atmosphere (Laffoley et al., 2009). The global average carbon storage in the top metre of salt marsh soils is approximately 255 MgC ha^{-1} (with a range of $16\text{--}623 \text{ MgC ha}^{-1}$) (IPCC 2013). However, many salt marshes have carbon stored to depths of as much as 6 m below the surface, making the above estimates conservative (Johnson et al., 2016).

Tidal flats are coastal habitats located adjacent to vegetated areas and characterized by mud accumulation and intertidal sand due to a heavy sediment inflow. Especially in estuaries, the tidal flats have a high carbon sequestration capacity, due to the large quantities of organic matter supplied by the riverine sediment and by the hydrodynamic environment which promotes carbon burial. For example, in the estuaries of the Amazon River due to the high riverine inputs the carbon storage is estimated to be particularly high ($514.2 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1}$ Sanders et al., 2010).

Figure 2 Images of habitat: a) seagrass, b) salt marsh c) mangrove, d) tidal flat. Sources: a , c) WWF; b, d) Wikipedia

Based on current mapping efforts, **blue carbon ecosystems (BCEs)** encompass approximately 360,000 to 1,850,000 km² within the world's coastal zones, representing about 0.5% of the seafloor. The wide range of the estimated area is due to large uncertainties in the distribution of seagrass meadows and tidal marshes. These ecosystems could potentially hold around 8.9 to 32.6 PgC in their soils and biomass, contributing over 50% of the global carbon burial in the ocean (Macreadie et al., 2021) (Table 1).

However, BCEs are highly threatened by various pressures, such as continuous coastal development, sea level rise, destructive fishing techniques, and coastal erosion. The degradation of these ecosystems has weakened their capacity to store carbon in sediments and has led to significant net greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. For example, globally, tidal flat ecosystems have been estimated to be reduced by 16% (over 20,000 km²) since 1984, significantly diminishing their capacity to provide essential ecosystem services (Murray et al., 2019), but also diminishing global potential for carbon sequestration and storage.

Table 1: Literature data related to the habitat area extension (km²), carbon sequestration accumulation rate (TgC^y⁻¹) carbon stock estimates (PgC) and relative reference. The * indicates the reference related to the carbon stock estimates. **CAR estimates and **Cstock estimates are from Chen and Lee, 2022. Adapted from Chen and Lee, 2022b.

BCE	Region	Area (km ²)	CAR coefficient (gC m ⁻² y ⁻¹)		Cstocks coefficient (Mg C ha ⁻¹)		CAR (Tg C y ⁻¹)		Cstocks (PgC)		Reference
			mean	± SE	mean	± SE	mean	± SE	mean	± SE	
Tidal flats	Global	127,921.00	129.80	29.90	86.30	29.90	16.60	3.80	1.10	0.10	Murray et al., 2019
			median: 53		median: 67.9		median: 6.80		median: 0.9		Macready et al., 2021
Mangroves	Global	81,485 - 137,600	230.90	26.00	293.90	7.20	18.8 - 31.6		2.4 - 4		Breithaupt et al., 2012
			median: NA		median: 237.4		median: NA		median: 1.9 - 3.3		Ouyang and Lee 2020
Salt Marshes	Global	41,657.00	244.70	26.10	317.20	19.10	10.20	1.10	1.30	0.10	Ouyang and Lee 2014
			median: NA		median: 282.2		median: NA		median: 1.20		Alongi 2018
Seagrasses	Global	160,387.00	138.00	38.00	194.20	20.20	22.10	6.10	3.10	0.30	McKenzie et al., 2020
			median: NA		median: 139.7		median: NA		median: 2.20		Mcleod et al., 2011; Fourquaran et al., 2012

7.2 Methods

The analysis focuses on the assessment of the carbon sequestration accumulation rate and carbon stock stored by the Atlantic Ocean coastal ecosystems (i.e. BCE) and it is related to the below-ground pool.

To calculate carbon storage at the Atlantic scale, we downloaded the global databases of the habitats constituent the blue carbon ecosystems (BCE), namely tidal flats, mangroves, seagrasses, and salt marshes. The aim is to determine the spatial extent at the Atlantic scale and then convert the extension to carbon accumulation rate and carbon storage for each ecosystem through coefficients extracted from literature. The calculations and data processing were done using R Studio version 4.4.0.

The spatial extension of each habitat is derived from the Ocean Data Viewer from United Nations Environmental Programme - World Conservation Monitoring Centre UNEP-WCMC (<https://data.unep-wcmc.org>). Data from mangroves were downloaded from Global Mangrove Watch website (<https://www.globalmangrovetwatch.org>) which provides remote sensing data and tools for monitoring mangroves. The spatial data extraction methodology followed the methodology of Halpern et al., (2012).

The data were extracted at the country level including both the marine (EEZ definition) and the land extension (50 km inland) due to the high inland extension of some habitats, e.g. tidal flats and salt marshes. Following recent updates relative to seagrass extension in some West African countries, such as Guinea and Guinea-Bissau, we have updated the data using the outcomes of the ResilienSea project for the West African countries and merged them with the data extracted from the UNEP-WCMC data (Mwikamba et al., 2024).

In this work we assess the 2 components of the carbon sequestration service: 1) the accumulation rate, and 2) the stock of carbon in the below-ground sediments only.

To assess the carbon accumulation rate at the Atlantic level we have converted the area extension of each BCE by the Carbon Accumulation Rate (CAR) ($\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$) for each single habitat (Chen & Lee 2022b), according to the Eq. 5.

$$C_{CAR} = A_i * CAR_i \quad (5)$$

where: A is the extent of habitat i in km^2 , and w is the carbon accumulation rate (CAR) per habitat i in ($\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$) as in Table 1.

To assess the carbon stock at the Atlantic level we have multiplied the extension of each BCE by the mean of the carbon stock estimates (MgC ha^{-1}) for each single habitat, described in Chen & Lee (2022b) (see Table SUMMARY_AREA_CSTOCK), according to Eq. 6.

$$C_{stock} = A_i * Coeff_{stock} \quad (6)$$

Where A is the extent of habitat i in km^2 , and $\text{Coeff}_{\text{stock}}$ is the estimate of carbon stock per habitat i in (MgC ha^{-1}) as in Table 1.

7.3 Results

Area coverage and carbon storage total and by country

Table 2 shows that the total area of blue carbon ecosystems (BCEs) in the Atlantic is $273,600 \text{ km}^2$. There are 117 countries bordering the Atlantic Ocean, and the country with the largest BCE coverage in the Atlantic Ocean is the United States ($40,543 \text{ km}^2$).

Seagrass has the largest extent, covering 54% of this area, with a total of $145,814.92 \text{ km}^2$. However, taking into account the new data from the ResilienceSea project, we have adjusted the km^2 estimates for two countries, Guinea and Guinea-Bissau, and calculated the area sampled to be 14.99 km^2 for Guinea and 3.43 km^2 for Guinea-Bissau.

According to literature estimates, the global coverage of **tidal flats** extending along the global coastlines between 60°N and 60°S ranges from $127,921 \text{ km}^2$ to $153,489 \text{ km}^2$ as detailed in Table 2. In the Atlantic Ocean, the **tidal flats** have an extension of $42,719.5 \text{ km}^2$ representing 15% of the BCE area in Atlantic, and 19.52% (see Table 2) of the global extent, while **salt marshes** are the least extended BCE in the Atlantic Ocean, covering $28,399.54 \text{ km}^2$, representing 10.57% of the Atlantic basin and 68.18% of the global extent. **Mangroves** cover $57,420.60 \text{ km}^2$ in the Atlantic Ocean, representing 21.95% of the area and 41.73% of the global extent (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Percentage distribution of the BCEs in the Atlantic Ocean according to the data extracted from Ocean Data Viewer UNEP-WCMC (<https://data.unep-wcmc.org>).

Considering the conversion factors obtained from the literature (Table 2), the total carbon accumulation rate in the Atlantic is estimated to be 46.81 TgCy^{-1} , while the total carbon stock, which represents the total carbon sequestered below-ground in Atlantic coastal ecosystems, is estimated to be 4.5 PgC , PgC which represents the 44 % of the global C_{stock} estimates (7.6 PgC).

Figure 4: (A) Carbon accumulation rate ($TgCy^{-1}$) for each BCEs : mangroves, salt marshes, seagrass meadows, and tidal flats. (B) Carbon stock estimates (PgC) for each BCES in mangroves, salt marshes, seagrass meadows, and tidal flats. The seagrass values, considering the ResilienSEA data would be $16.60TgCy^{-1}$ for the flux and $1.68PgC$ for the stock.

Table 2: The table reports the total area for each blue carbon habitat, computed in this study, and the carbon stock for each habitat. **The mean and median of C stock estimates are from Chen and Lee (2022). The original results of this work are reported in bold. The value in parentheses * represents the adjusted results with not UNEP seagrass coverage in GUinea and Guinea Bissau.

BCE	Region	Area (km ²)	CAR coefficient (MgC ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹)		CAR (Tg C y ⁻¹)		Cstocks coefficient**(Mg C ha ⁻¹)	Cstocks (PgC _{org})	Reference
			mean	SE					
Tidal flats	Global	127,921.00	mean	SE 0.30	16.6	3.8	median: 67.9	0.9	Macready et al., 2021
	Atlantic	42,719.50	1.30		5.54			0.29	This study
Mangroves	Global	109,543	mean	SE 0.26	18.8 - 31.6		median: 237.4	1.9 - 3.3	Ouyang and Lee 2020 (averaged)
	Atlantic	57,420.6	2.31		13.26			1.36	This study
Salt Marshes	Global	41,657.00	mean	SE 0.26	10.2	1.1	median: 282.2	1.2	Alongi 2018
	Atlantic	28,400.32	2.45		6.95			0.8	This study
Seagrasses	Global	160,387.00	mean	SE 0.38	22.1	6.1	median: 139.7	2.2	Mcleod et al., 2011; Fourquaran et al., 2012
	Atlantic	145,059 (112,269*)	1.38		20.01 - (15.55*)			2.03 (1.57*)	This study
TOTAL	Global	439,507.50			80.5			7.6	
	Atlantic	273,599.42			45.77 (40.6*)			4.48 (3.9*)	

The accumulation rate by seagrass is 20.12 TgCy⁻¹ and storage is 2.04 PgC (median), which is the largest contribution to Cstock in the Atlantic and accounts for 47 % of total Atlantic BCE carbon storage (Table 2, Figure 4).

Mangroves make the second largest contribution with a carbon accumulation rate of 13.26 TgCy⁻¹ and storage of 1.36 PgC, representing 30% of the Atlantic BCE Cstock and 50.9% of global mangrove carbon storage.

The carbon sequestration accumulation rate in the tidal flats is 5.54 TgCy⁻¹, while the total storage is 0.29 PgC (5%).

The carbon accumulation rate in the salt marshes is estimated at 6.95 TgCy⁻¹, while the storage amount is 0.80 PgC. Despite their relatively small area (28,400.32 km², 11% of the Atlantic BCEs), the Atlantic coasts contribute the largest share of carbon storage in salt marshes with 72 % in the Atlantic Ocean (see Table 2) (Figure 5).

The countries with the largest carbon stock in their BCEs are the United States (814.8 TgC, 18% of the total), Mexico (362 TgC, 8% of the total), and Nigeria (351 TgC, 8% of the total) (Figure 6).

Figure 5: The maps represent the A) Carbon stock (TgC) from BCEs for each Atlantic country; B) Carbon accumulation rate (TgCy-1)

Figure 6: The histogram shows the carbon storage (in TgC) of the first 10 countries (out of 117), divided by habitat type (mangroves in red, salt marshes in green, seagrass in blue and tidal flat in purple).

7.4 Discussion

The global interest in BCEs is based on their potential to mitigate climate change, including conservation and restoration strategies. At the same time, their conservation benefits the marine environment's health and provides numerous ecosystem services such as coastal protection from storms and flooding, maintaining water quality, promoting biodiversity, providing food for sustainable livelihoods, and acting as nursery areas for many marine species.

Blue carbon is the carbon captured and stored in coastal wetlands such as mangroves, salt (intertidal) marshes and seagrasses, as well as in marine ecosystems, where it is retained in both biomass and sediments (Convention on Wetlands). Much of this carbon is deposited in soils and sediments, leading to long-term carbon accumulation (Chmura et al., 2003). The carbon sink process associated with the burial of carbon in sediments is estimated to be 55 times faster than in tropical rainforests (McLeod et al., 2011).

However, these ecosystems are heavily impacted by human activities. According to the literature, all BCE have declined over the last century, with mangroves declining at a rate of 1-3%, mainly due to aquaculture, land-use change and land reclamation (Macreadie et al., 2019). The decline since 1897 (first recorded) is estimated at 29% for seagrasses, with the decline accelerating sevenfold since 1990 (Waycott et al., 2009). Considering both salt marshes and tidal flats, the minimum global rate of loss is estimated to be 1–2% per year (Duarte et al. 2008).

Much research is still being done to understand the extent to which disturbance can affect the sequestration of carbon in sediments, but it is agreed that this depends mainly on the depth of the soil at which the disturbance occurs and the proportion of disturbed carbon that is lost as CO₂.

Since this attention to the topic, many efforts have been made to produce accurate estimates of global BCE, but there is still a great deal of uncertainty as the available distributional data is highly skewed geographically (and historically) (Macreadie et al., 2019, Mwikamba et al., 2024).

The results show that tidal flats and salt marshes have the lowest values for carbon fluxes and storage (see Table 1). This can primarily be attributed to the limited availability of detritus from vascular plants in tidal flats, where carbon storage is primarily influenced by microphytobenthos, the main primary producers in these areas and a crucial nutrient source for the benthic food web. Sedimentation in tidal flats is closely linked to fluvial processes, with estuaries, which have a high load of suspended sediments and nutrient inputs, being the main contributors of organic matter in these environments. In contrast, the structural features of mangroves and seagrasses — such as their aerial roots and shoots — help to dampen waves, reduce currents and facilitate the accumulation of organic matter, thereby promoting carbon storage (Chen and Lee, 2022b).

An important aspect to highlight is that to have a complete assessment of the marine carbon sequestration service, many components are lacking. Indeed, just remaining on the coastal regions, a controversial aspect related to the BCE is whether **algae** should be included in the BCE. Macroalgae are the most important primary producers in the coastal zone with an estimated area of 3.5 million km². The main resistance to the inclusion of macroalgae is related to the fact that macroalgae generally grow on hard or sandy substrates that have no or limited carbon storage potential. However, Krause-Jensen et al., (2016) have estimated that macroalgae growing in soft sediments have a global C burial rate of 6.2 Tg C y⁻¹ in their habitat. In addition, several studies

show that macroalgae act as C donors, with detached macroalgae being transported by currents and deposited in C sinks outside macroalgal habitats. Recent estimates suggest that up to 14 Tg C per year⁻¹ of macroalgae-derived particulate organic C is buried in shelf sediments and a further 153 Tg C y⁻¹ is sequestered in the deep ocean. This has been demonstrated, for example, by the presence of fresh Sargassum in abyssal isopods, by macroalgal drift in the abyssal canyons, and by the collection of sinking algal fragments in pelagic sediment traps in the open ocean at depths of up to 1900 m (Krause-Jensen et al., 2016). These calculations suggest that macroalgae may contribute to higher global C sequestration rates than seagrasses, tidal marshes, and mangroves combined (Krause-Jensen et al., 2016; Macreadie et al., 2019) (Table 3).

As we move further from coastal regions, the uncertainty surrounding which ocean areas should be included in carbon sequestration assessments increases. This uncertainty stems from both the challenges associated with evaluation and the absence of effective strategies for implementing mitigation or adaptation in these areas.

In the previous section, we discussed the assessment of carbon sequestration through the oceanic biological carbon pump (BCP). This process operates at the *microbial scale* through the activities of phytoplankton and bacteria, which facilitate carbon export via gravitational settling, ocean mixing, and downward migrations. The analysis presented here incorporates both conventional fluxes at fixed depths and a comprehensive carbon inventory across the entire water column. The estimated total for the BCP is 319.59 PgC (with a standard deviation of 50.47 from CMIP6 models), representing approximately 17% of the global BCP in the Atlantic and a flux rate of 293 TgC y⁻¹ below 1000 m. Recent estimates have expanded the discussion by emphasizing the role of krill in the Southern Ocean as a crucial carbon storage mechanism. Krill faecal pellets, moults, and carcasses significantly drive carbon fluxes to the ocean's interior through the biological carbon pump (BCP), yet this process remains underrepresented in existing models (Cavan et al., 2024). According to Cavan et al. (2024), the carbon contribution from krill during the Austral productive season is comparable to global blue carbon stores. While the carbon concentration from krill pellets (1.3 tC km² yr⁻¹) is three orders of magnitude lower than that of coastal blue carbon vegetation, the vast habitat of Antarctic krill, which covers 16–19 million km², compensates for this discrepancy (Table 3).

In addition, this assessment does not account for the carbon sequestered by the *physical carbon pump*, which involves the transfer of carbon through physical processes such as transport, mixing, and upwelling, responsible for the net uptake of carbon from the atmosphere.

Table 3: Comparison of carbon sequestration by different compartments of the marine ecosystems

Oceanic components	Zone	Area (km ²)	Carbon flux		Cstocks		Source
			Tg C y ⁻¹	units	Mg C ha ⁻¹	PgC	
Blue carbon ecosystems	Glo	439,507.50	80.5	CAR	~ 0.086	7.06	
	Atl	273,599.4	41.3	CAR		4.03	This study
Oceanic BCP	Atl	348,872,093					
		85,133,000	293	POC flux at 1000 m		319.59	<i>This study Del 3.2</i>
Krill (Southern Ocean) BCP	Glo (SO)	16,000,000	66			0.019	Cavan et al., 2024
						0.0137	
Seaweeds	Glo	35,000,000	6.2 -153				Krause-Jensen et al., (2016)
Marine sediments	Glo	348,872,093	-		6656	2322	Atwood et al., 2020
	Atl	85,133,000	-			566.65	

Another concern is the valuation of carbon sequestered in marine sediments, which are considered critical carbon reservoirs due to their large area and long-term carbon storage capacity of thousands to millions of years (Atwood et al., 2020). The main challenge is that there are no robust and spatially explicit estimates of carbon stocks in marine sediments. Recent modeling efforts (Atwood et al., 2020) have resulted in initial estimates of about 2322 PgC (6656 MgC km⁻²), with about 79% of this carbon stored in the abyssal and basin zones, making ocean sediments the largest carbon stored on Earth.

The gap in carbon estimation remains significant, and further assessments are necessary to enhance accuracy. Improved spatial data are essential to address geographic biases, while a deeper understanding of oceanographic processes is crucial for reducing uncertainty in these estimates.

8 Conclusions

The pluralistic valuation of ecosystem services presented in this report aims to increase understanding of the current socio-ecological wellbeing of the Atlantic Ocean as well as its contribution to the social and economic welfare of the communities depending upon it. To do so, we present and apply examples of ecosystem services assessment methodologies for provisioning, cultural and regulating services provided by the Atlantic Ocean. These encompass different industry sectors, marine and coastal tourism, and the general public and develop quantitative and qualitative descriptions of human-nature relationships (including nature's contributions to people), using monetary (Section 4), socio-cultural (Section 5) and biophysical (Sections 6, 7) value indicators.

Our analysis is necessarily composite in methods and approaches because of the nature of the ecosystem services assessed. While provisioning services might find direct economic translation into share of the Gross Value Added (GVA) (Section 4), sense of place, although quantifiable in monetary terms, relies on qualitative analysis of visitors' reviews extracted by analysing online Google Maps reviews (Section 5). The analysis of carbon storage processes relies on quantitative estimates of flows in both the open Atlantic Ocean (Section 6) and coastal Atlantic blue carbon ecosystems (Section 7) and couples these with "social cost of carbon" estimates.

The value of provisioning services by Atlantic coastal countries presented in Section 4 summarises the available data on the value of capture fisheries, aquaculture, minerals, non-renewable/renewable energy and coastal tourism from various sources. Overall, the results show that coastal tourism is the highest source of GVA for most countries among the sectors analysed, while fisheries and aquaculture are generally the lowest. Nevertheless, the proportions vary enormously across countries with a tendency for low income Atlantic African countries to have high GVA from fisheries and in few cases from minerals and non-renewables: for these countries the GVA from provisioning services account for a very large share of total country GVA (between 1% and 12%). Conversely in the wealthiest countries in temperate areas the GVA from tourism dominates and the GVA from provisioning services account to less than 1% of total country GVA. The large value of provisioning services from coastal tourism activities deserves a mention pointing out one of the limits of an assessment entirely based on economic considerations. Key activities, like food provision through fishing activity, rank low as value producers, being the economic wealth of modern economies based on the tertiary service sector. This leads to an underestimation of primary activities that very often carry with them values related to culture and identity. This is even more true for items like "landscape", "ecosystem" and "biodiversity".

Against this background, the analysis of Google Maps reviews in Section 5 represents a novel approach to assessing the value and utility of coastal/maritime attractions around the Atlantic that perfectly complements the pluralistic assessment of tourism-related services. Comments highlighted the importance of the linked OHI objectives: Sense of Place - places, Sense of Place – species, Tourism & Recreation, Livelihoods & Economies - economies, Biodiversity – species; Biodiversity – habitats, Clean Waters and the additional code 'clean sites', and the data collected could support future Ocean Health Index assessments. The socio-cultural benefits mentioned by the reviewers were related to almost 80 different types of recreational activities they can undertake at the sites, which provide different financial portfolios to local economies depending on the type of experiences and activities available. It is noteworthy that 10% of the evaluations consisted of negative

remarks and the reviewers pointed out various disadvantages of the sites: overcrowding of the site with people, lack of investment in the infrastructure of the site, presence of plastic and other waste on the site, no adequate management of biodiversity and degradation of biodiversity due to tourism. It is known that the presence of litter in the sea affects the aesthetic and recreational quality of visitors and has a detrimental effect on leisure activities and beach enjoyment. The analysis described in Section 5 found that the presence of plastics in protected and non-protected marine tourism areas is a significant detriment in terms of 'Sense of Place', 'Clean Waters' and 'clean site', highlighting the link between these three concepts and how the presence of plastics can negatively impact the attractiveness of special places for people. The results reflect the presence of a broad pattern of threats to iconic marine areas around the Atlantic that are very important in terms of revenue. Our estimated annual visitor revenue of nearly \$207 million at the sites studied demonstrates the public's desire to visit iconic marine areas and their willingness to pay for cultural services provided by healthy sites.

A quantitative estimate of carbon sequestration in the open ocean is presented in Section 6 using both conventional fluxes at fixed depth and a comprehensive carbon inventory for the entire water column using model estimates. The results show that the Atlantic Ocean exhibits different patterns of carbon flux to the deep ocean that vary with the latitudinal gradient: low carbon export is observed in the subtropical gyres, while the tropical and upwelling regions, which are characterized by higher productivity, show higher export. In addition, the North Atlantic is a region with high carbon exports due to its high productivity, cold water temperature and deep winter mixed layers. The Southern Ocean is the region where the available models are more uncertain. The results show that the methodology applied to the Earth system models tends to overestimate the sequestration inventory compared to the literature results. The total carbon stock of the Atlantic is in the order of 260-375 PgC (average 319.49 PgC; about 15-20% of the global ocean carbon stock), with the average value of this output ranging from US\$46.6 trillion to US\$171 trillion.

- In Section 7, the blue carbon sequestered and stored in coastal wetlands such as mangroves, salt marshes and seagrasses was estimated for the Atlantic Ocean, which covers an area of about 273,000 km². These areas are able to store about 4 PgC of carbon through biomass and carbon sequestration in the sediment. This is two orders of magnitude less than the carbon stocks in the open ocean. However, considering the other values that coastal blue carbon has for services such as tourism, coastal defence and sense of place, the value of blue carbon ecosystems cannot be dismissed.

As far as we are aware, this is the first pluralistic valuation of ecosystem services conducted at the Atlantic Ocean scale which measures and makes visible the values relating to key aspects of the marine biosphere. While the resulting values may at first glance seem incommensurable since they deal with monetary, socio-cultural and biophysical indicators, together they highlight the huge benefits that the Atlantic Ocean brings to society. These values should be treated in parallel and as equally important rather than traded-off in decision-making processes (Pascual et al., 2023). Moreover, it has to be stressed that these services are provided by healthy oceans: biodiversity plays a critical role in delivering the key provisioning, cultural and regulating services identified in our research and is a common thread that has emerged from our pluralistic approach. Our interdisciplinary analysis has demonstrated that Atlantic Ocean biodiversity is (in)directly of significant importance to humans due to the instrumental (e.g. monetary), relational (e.g. sense of place) and intrinsic (e.g. carbon cycling) values held by those benefiting from the contributions that existing biodiversity makes to the functioning of the ocean.

Pluralistic valuations enable the ecosystem services concept to operate as a boundary object, facilitating communication and cooperation between different user groups working in different contexts and with different worldviews (Ainscough et al., and authors therein). The findings can help policymakers develop better informed and more inclusive coastal management decision-making policies and processes regarding the Atlantic Ocean socio-ecological system based on the stakeholders identified in our research and the resulting data. Integrating valuations of monetary, socio-cultural and biophysical value indicators into a pluralistic approach emphasises the interconnected nature of the provisioning, cultural and regulating services analysed and underscores the critical role that existing biodiversity plays in the functioning of the ocean. This holistic approach helps to avoid concerns about economic valuations of ecosystem services that might provide a rationale for environmental degradation (Ainscough et al., 2019). Conversely, the pluralistic valuations provided here represent a unifying framework that can be a basis for policy makers to highlight the benefits that humankind can receive from a healthy ocean.

Overall this report sheds light on the considerable value that the ocean has through direct benefits such as provisioning and culture, and indirect services like carbon storage. More than ever the analysis reveals a global and shared interest to maintain the system at its best health condition since the services are interlinked and affect the Atlantic Ocean's capabilities to provide them. Undoubtedly, the most important next step in ecosystem services valuation is to operationalize an integrated valuation framework that endorses 'value pluralism' to better support global policy initiatives focused on marine and coastal ecosystems, where blue activities are increasingly becoming important drivers of change. In this way, a greater portion of society will be involved in assessing the value of ecosystem services and both 'natural capital' and 'social capital' will be further integrated within national and global accounts of economic development.

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10 Appendices

Table S1: Sources of entrance fee and visitor number data for individual case study sites.

Case study site name	Entrance fee	Estimated annual visitor numbers
Víkurfjara Black Sand Beach	N/A	N/A
Ytre Hvaler Nasjonalpark	N/A	N/A
Skomer Island	https://www.welshwildlife.org/skomer-island-day-trips	https://www.itv.com/news/wales/2024-04-23/puffin-population-in-skomer-islands-a-slight-dip-in-numbers
Parque Nacional Marítimo-Terrestre de las Islas Atlánticas de Galicia	N/A	https://www.xunta.gal/es/notas-de-prensa/-/nova/000053/xunta-destaca-contribucion-las-empresas-del-parque-nacional-maritimo-terrestre
Parque Natural do Sudoeste Alentejano y Costa Vicentina	N/A	https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Parque_natural_del_Suroeste_Alentejano_y_Costa_Vicentina
Bahía de Dakhla	N/A	https://www.atalayar.com/articulo/economia-y-empresas/dajla-cierra-ano-doble-turistas-pesar-covid-19/20220112115034154592.html
Praia do Fogo	N/A	https://www.theportugalnews.com/es/noticias/2024-05-12/aumentan-los-visitantes-internacionales-a-las-azores/88720
Basin Head Provincial Park	N/A	https://www.dfo-mpo.gc.ca/oceans/publications/basinhead-management-gestion-2021-2026/index-eng.html
Cape Cod National Seashore	https://www.nps.gov/caco/planyourvisit/basicinfo.htm	https://www.capecodchamber.org/explore/cape-cod-national-seashore/
Parque Nacional Ciénaga de Zapata	N/A	https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ci%C3%A9naga_de_Zapata
Playa el Yaque	N/A	N/A

Los Corales del Rosario y de San Bernardo	https://old.parquesnacionales.gov.co/portal/es/derechos-de-ingreso/	https://old.parquesnacionales.gov.co/portal/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/informe-del-comportamiento-de-visitantes-en-pn-n-ano-2021-actualizado.pdf
Parque Nacional Natural Tayrona	https://www.radionacional.co/cultural/turismo/precio-de-ingreso-parque-tayrona-2024-para-colombianos-y-extranjeros	https://old.parquesnacionales.gov.co/portal/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/informe-del-comportamiento-de-visitantes-en-pn-n-ano-2021-actualizado.pdf
Cayos Miskitos y Franja Costera Inmediata	N/A	N/A
Reserva de la Biósfera Sian Ka'an	https://mihuellaxelmundo.com/excursion-a-la-reserva-de-sian-kaan-riviera-maya/	https://issuu.com/dcasaveronica/docs/revista_24_pginas/14753376
Laguna Madre y Delta del Río Bravo	https://www.cofemersimir.gob.mx/expediente/27615/mir/53466/anexo/6810346	https://wli.wwt.org.uk/?member=area-de-proteccion-de-flora-y-fauna-laguna-madre-y-delta-del-rio-bravo
Everglades National Park	https://www.nps.gov/ever/planyourvisit/fees.htm	https://www.nationalparks.org/explore/parks/everglades-national-park
Parque Nacional Marinho de Fernando de Noronha	https://www.parnanoronha.com.br/en/visitante	https://efeagro.com/noronha-paraiso-turismo-bolsonaro/
Parque Nacional Marinho de Abrolhos	https://www.wikiparques.org/wiki/Parque_Nacional_Marinho_dos_Abrolhos	https://wli.wwt.org.uk/es/2013/02/centro-de-visitantes-do-parque-nacional-marinho-dos-abrolhos-icmbio/
Boa Vista	N/A	https://viajaracaboverde.com/isla-de-boavista/
Bojo Beach	https://www.tripadvisor.com/Attraction_Review-g293797-d1195610-Reviews-Bojo_Beach-Accra_Greater_Accra.html	N/A
Península Valdés	https://peninsulavaldes.org.ar/visita-peninsula/valor-de-ingreso/	https://chubutpatagonia.gob.ar/chubut-registro-record-de-visitantes-en-la-anp-peninsula-valdes-y-punta-loma-durante-el-2022/
Skeleton Coast National Park	https://www.nwr.com.au/icheephu/2021/04/Press-release-Park-fees-2021.pdf	https://safariants.com/sg-safari/skeleton-coast-national-park/

Table S2: Total area coverage and total carbon storage by the total of Blue carbon ecosystems in the Atlantic Ocean.

rgn_nam	TOT km2	TOT_CFlux_area CAR_TgCy_1	TOT_CStock_TgC median
Albania	135.56	0.02	2.37
Algeria	56.49	0.01	0.73
Angola	1237.38	0.20	18.26
Anguilla	23.70	0.00	0.31
Antigua and Barbuda	353.81	0.05	4.53
Argentina	2557.10	0.47	42.88
Aruba	40.78	0.01	0.56
Ascension	0.00	0.00	0.00
Azores	7.37	0.00	0.05
Bahamas	5930.65	0.94	84.57
Barbados	113.07	0.02	1.54
Belgium	20.78	0.00	0.22
Belize	6209.09	0.91	91.79
Benin	42.33	0.01	0.75
Bermuda	2.75	0.00	0.02
Bosnia and Herzegovina	0.00	0.00	0.00
Bouvet Island	0.00	0.00	0.00
Brazil	16637.74	3.33	311.71
British Virgin Islands	57.16	0.01	0.73

Cameroon	2530.29	0.53	50.57
Canada	3867.19	0.55	34.35
Canary Islands	2376.26	0.33	33.09
Cape Verde	15.89	0.00	0.11
Cayman Islands	109.58	0.02	1.95
Colombia	1572.37	0.29	28.11
Costa Rica	45.50	0.01	0.31
Croatia	324.65	0.05	4.59
Cuba	20389.80	3.13	312.69
Curacao	5.70	0.00	0.05
Cyprus	113.59	0.02	1.79
Democratic Republic of the Congo	290.54	0.06	5.92
Denmark	2332.19	0.35	31.69
Dominica	604.44	0.08	8.39
Dominican Republic	610.24	0.10	10.10
Egypt	120.58	0.02	0.84
Equatorial Guinea	450.47	0.08	7.25
Estonia	8.88	0.00	0.25
Faeroe Islands	0.00	0.00	0.00
Falkland Islands	40.20	0.01	0.27
Finland	132.76	0.03	3.75
France	4036.81	0.63	53.53

French Guiana	1212.62	0.22	19.05
Gabon	2124.79	0.45	44.18
Gambia	448.36	0.10	9.51
Germany	3887.73	0.53	33.60
Ghana	3481.43	0.50	49.45
Greece	781.67	0.11	10.63
Greenland	5.73	0.00	0.05
Grenada	16.29	0.00	0.23
Guadeloupe and Martinique	1555.63	0.22	22.12
Guatemala	22.41	0.00	0.30
Guernsey	15.30	0.00	0.10
Guinea	2731.02	0.58	56.38
Guinea Bissau	3731.22	0.75	70.30
Guyana	1391.12	0.21	14.46
Haiti	1026.48	0.15	15.56
Honduras	3455.41	0.50	50.38
Iceland	26.52	0.01	0.75
Ireland	931.87	0.14	9.03
Israel	22.37	0.00	0.28
Italy	4927.88	0.73	74.16
Ivory Coast	289.65	0.04	2.90
Jamaica	1015.79	0.15	15.08
Jan Mayen	0.00	0.00	0.00
Jersey	36.91	0.00	0.25
Latvia	1.61	0.00	0.05

Lebanon	0.40	0.00	0.00
Liberia	250.05	0.05	4.67
Libya	46.49	0.01	0.40
Lithuania	0.11	0.00	0.00
Madeira	4.89	0.00	0.03
Malta	79.11	0.01	1.11
Mauritania	448.37	0.06	3.07
Mexico	20474.70	3.59	363.11
Monaco	0.00	0.00	0.00
Montenegro	18.53	0.00	0.15
Montserrat	2.71	0.00	0.02
Morocco	114.34	0.01	0.78
Namibia	81.24	0.01	0.56
Netherlands	1443.51	0.21	14.70
Nicaragua	6852.53	0.98	98.67
Nigeria	19691.23	3.49	349.92
Northern Saint-Martin	8.46	0.00	0.06
Norway	85.94	0.01	1.17
Panama	2405.90	0.35	33.78
Poland	24.27	0.00	0.19
Portugal	578.85	0.11	9.93
Puerto Rico and Virgin Islands of the United States	954.33	0.14	14.68
Republique du Congo	36.28	0.01	0.60
Saba	0.00	0.00	0.00

Saint Kitts and Nevis	72.23	0.01	0.99
Saint Lucia	25.00	0.00	0.29
Saint Pierre and Miquelon	5.65	0.00	0.04
Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	11.23	0.00	0.08
Sao Tome and Principe	0.87	0.00	0.02
Senegal	3198.09	0.56	55.33
Sierra Leone	6922.90	1.09	108.98
Sint Eustatius	0.30	0.00	0.00
Sint Maarten	32.19	0.00	0.43
Slovenia	2.41	0.00	0.06
South Africa	227.35	0.04	2.82
South Georgia and the South Sandwich Islands	162.95	0.02	1.11
Spain	4726.18	0.85	89.04
Suriname	1537.66	0.28	24.53
Sweden	159.08	0.03	2.43
Syria	0.30	0.00	0.00
Togo	8.67	0.00	0.06
Trinidad and Tobago	124.66	0.03	2.34
Tristan da Cunha	0.20	0.00	0.00

Tunisia	6036.75	0.83	82.17
Turkey	302.88	0.07	7.55
Turks and Caicos Islands	1558.06	0.23	20.92
United Kingdom	4674.64	0.70	50.57
United States	38206.39	7.23	763.46
Uruguay	59.45	0.01	0.95
Venezuela	10143.17	1.92	187.52
Western Sahara	53.53	0.01	0.37